

**A Comparative Study of Work-Family Conflict, Perceived Flexibility
Requirement, Work Autonomy, Job Performance and Perceived
Organizational Support among Indian IT Employees across Sex and Work
Arrangement**

M. SC DISSERTATION

IN

APPLIED PSYCHOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to assess work-family conflict, perceived flexibility requirement, work autonomy, job performance, and perceived organizational support among the Indian IT employees in respect of sex and work arrangement. A total number of 154 IT employees, including 79 males and 75 females were selected using purposive sampling technique. The sample comprised employees placed under different modes of work (50 under on-site, 54 under hybrid, and 50 under remote work arrangements).

The tools used in the study included Work-Family Conflict Scale (Netemeyer, Boles, and McMurrian, 1996), Perceived Flexibility Requirements Scale (Höge and Hornung, 2015), Work Autonomy Scale (Breugh, 1985), Job Performance Scale (Çalışkan and Köroğlu, 2022), and Survey of Perceived Organizational Support – 8-item version (Eisenberger et al., 1986), and a General Information Schedule.

The findings revealed that male and female IT employees did not differ significantly in respect of any of the selected psychological variables. However, males reported slightly higher perceived flexibility requirements than females; whereas females reported marginally higher work-family conflict, work autonomy, job performance, and perceived organizational support than their male counterparts.

With respect to work arrangement, IT employees placed under different work modes did not differ significantly regarding work-family conflict, perceived flexibility requirement, and job performance. However, significant differences were recorded between the workers under remote and on-site modes in respect of specific dimensions of work autonomy, i.e., work scheduling and work criteria autonomy, as well as perceived organizational support. The highest level of work-family conflict was experienced by on-site employees, while the lowest was observed among remote employees. Workers under hybrid mode showed the highest

perceived flexibility requirement, whereas remote employees reported the lowest. Regarding work autonomy, remote workers reported the highest level, while on-site employees expressed the lowest. Remote workers also reported the highest level of job performance, while on-site employees displayed the lowest. Regarding perceived organizational support, remote employees felt the most supported, whereas on-site employees reported the least.

Keywords: Work-Family Conflict, Perceived Flexibility Requirement, Work Autonomy, Job Performance, Perceived Organizational Support

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PREFACE

The global shift in work culture, catalysed by the COVID-19 pandemic, forced organizations across the world to revisit the very foundations of how, where, and why work is done. Amidst this disruption, remote and hybrid work models emerged not just as survival mechanisms, but as sustainable alternatives to traditional on-site employment. While technological adaptation was swift, the psychological transition for employees has been far more layered. It is in this evolving context that the current research is situated, an effort to understand how different work arrangements influence the lived experiences of professionals, particularly in the high-paced and demanding world of India's Information Technology (IT) sector. The IT industry, long celebrated as the backbone of India's digital economy, has always been marked by rapid innovation, high expectations, and global connectivity. However, the pandemic-era acceleration of remote work exposed new psychological terrains blurring work-life boundaries, reshaping autonomy, altering performance dynamics, and influencing perceptions of support from organizations.

The present research seeks to explore and compare how employees working in on-site, hybrid, and remote models differ in their experiences of five key psychological constructs, namely, work-family conflict, perceived flexibility requirement, work autonomy, job performance, and perceived organizational support. These constructs reflect not only professional wellbeing, but also contribute to broader conversations about employee engagement, retention, and the future of work in the digital age. This study becomes especially relevant in a country like India, where sociocultural factors, familial responsibilities, and economic diversity significantly shape one's relationship with work. With a large share of the workforce in the IT sector being relatively young, digitally competent, and aspirational, understanding the psychological implications of flexible work becomes a necessary step toward designing people-first organizations. The question is no longer whether remote or hybrid work

is feasible, but rather how these arrangements can be optimized for employee well-being, performance, and organizational success.

The findings from this study highlight the subtle psychological shifts taking place in the Indian workplace. These insights are expected to inform human resource strategies, organizational policies, and broader discourses on work design, and psychological health in knowledge-based industries. I chose working IT professionals from different states and union territories of India as representatives of the modern workforce navigating this transition. Their perspectives shaped by gender, role, work experience, and context offer a rich dataset to reflect upon the broader psychological landscape of India's digital professionals. I sincerely hope that this research contributes to a deeper understanding of employee needs, and serves as a foundation for creating more empathetic, inclusive, and sustainable workplaces.

With this preface, I would like to humbly state that I have attempted to carry out the present research with integrity, sincerity, and academic commitment. May this work serve as a small but meaningful contribution toward building a future of work that values not just productivity, but also psychological well-being.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

“Work is not just about earning a living—it is also about contributing to society, expressing identity, and achieving purpose.” – Richard Sennett

Work is not merely a mechanism of earning a livelihood; it is a multidimensional domain that influences psychological well-being, shape’s identity, and impacts family life. In recent years, the workplace has undergone significant restructuring, particularly with the emergence of hybrid and remote work models. These developments have further been propelled by technological advancements and the global disruption caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. As organizations shift from conventional on-site models to more flexible work arrangements, the implications for employee experience, motivation, and performance are being re-examined with renewed urgency.

In the Indian context, the Information Technology sector has emerged as a leading adopter of evolving work models. With a large, young, and skilled workforce, this industry has integrated hybrid and remote work into its core operations. However, these arrangements do not only alter logistical frameworks; they also reshape psychological variables, such as perceived flexibility, autonomy, organizational support, and work-family conflict, all of which can directly or indirectly affect employee job performance. Hence, it becomes timely and essential in understanding how these diverse work arrangements influence the key psychosocial outcomes.

Significance of Work Arrangements in Organizational Psychology

Influence on Employee Experience:

Work arrangements are instrumental in defining the structural and psychological boundaries of work. The traditional on-site model fosters close supervision and immediate collaboration, yet may limit flexibility and autonomy. In contrast, hybrid and remote models

promise greater control over time and space, but may pose challenges, such as social isolation, blurred work-life boundaries, and reduced managerial support.

Impact on Organizational Outcomes:

Understanding the impact of work arrangements on employee outcomes is essential for improving organizational performance and employee well-being. Appropriate structuring of work formats can lead to reduced stress, higher retention, improved engagement, and increased productivity - key goals for any knowledge-driven industry.

Relevance to Indian IT Sector:

India's IT sector employs millions of professionals, many of whom are in the early stages of their careers. These individuals often juggle personal and professional roles, making them highly sensitive to changes in the work structures. A nuanced understanding of how work arrangements affect them can inform HR strategies and policy formulation within and beyond the sector.

Work-Family Conflict

In an increasingly dynamic and interconnected world of work, the boundaries between professional and personal lives are becoming increasingly porous. This phenomenon has given rise to the concept of Work-Family Conflict (WFC). It is a psychological state in which competing demands from work and family roles hinder one another, leading to emotional strain and role overload. Greenhaus and Beutell (1985) defined work-family conflict as a form of inter-role conflict wherein the role pressures from the work and family domains are mutually incompatible, such that participation in one role makes it more difficult to participate in the other.

The prevalence of work-family conflict is particularly high in sectors characterized by demanding workloads and time-sensitive deliverables, Information Technology (IT) industry being one such sector. Employees in this sector often face long working hours, tight deadlines,

and performance-driven environments, which can impair their ability to fulfil family responsibilities, resulting in a compromised sense of well-being and work satisfaction.

Theoretical Framework Underpinning Work-Family Conflict

Role Theory:

According to Greenhaus and Beutell (1985), Role Theory is one of the most frequently applied frameworks to explain work-family conflict (WFC). This theory was initially conceptualised by Kahn et al. (1964), and was later extended by various scholars to explain the psychological strain that emerges when individuals attempt to meet the expectations of multiple social roles simultaneously. Since its introduction, Role Theory has been widely used in the domains of Organizational Behaviour, Sociology, Psychology, and Family Studies to understand how individuals manage overlapping responsibilities in their professional and personal lives.

Role Theory posits that individuals hold multiple roles, such as employee, parent, spouse, caregiver etc., each with specific behavioural expectations, norms, and responsibilities. Conflict arises when the demands of one role interfere with the capacity to fulfil the expectations of another, leading to a form of psychological strain known as inter-role conflict. In the context of work-family dynamics, this conflict manifests in two key dimensions:

1. **Work Interfering with Family (WIF):** It occurs when one's occupational responsibilities hinder his or her performance or involvement in family roles. This may include long work hours, excessive job stress, or inflexible schedule that leave little room for personal obligations.
2. **Family Interfering with Work (FIW):** It arises when family demands or crises disrupt an individual's capacity to perform at work. This may stem from caregiving responsibilities, household duties, or emotional strain within the family setting.

Greenhaus and Beutell (1985) suggested that the level of work-family conflict experienced by an individual is influenced by three primary role characteristics, that is, time-based conflict strain-based conflict, and behaviour-based conflict.

- *Time-based conflict*: It occurs when time devoted to one role makes it difficult to participate in another.
- *Strain-based conflict*: It occurs when stress or fatigue from one role impairs performance in another.
- *Behaviour-based conflict*: It occurs when behaviours required in one role are incompatible with those expected in another.

These dimensions form the theoretical basis for understanding the psychological mechanisms through which work and family demands clash. Moreover, scholars have highlighted the moderating role of role salience, that is, the personal importance attributed to a given role. Individuals who strongly identify with their professional roles, for instance, may perceive higher conflict when family demands intrude upon work responsibilities, and vice versa.

Role Theory Framework of Work-Family Conflict

Correlates and Influencing Factors of Work-Family Conflict

Work-family conflict is not experienced in isolation; rather, exists at the intersection of personal characteristics, organizational structures, and broader social dynamics. At the individual level, work-family conflict has been found to be positively correlated with stress,

burnout, and anxiety, and negatively associated with job satisfaction and overall well-being (Choi et al., 2016; Mohammed et al., 2022). These outcomes are especially pronounced in high-demand industries like IT, where performance pressures and long work hours are the norm.

The experience of work-family conflict is further shaped by gendered social expectations, which influence how individuals prioritise and navigate their work and family roles. For instance, women in dual-earner households often report higher levels of family-to-work conflict, as domestic responsibilities tend to affect them disproportionately. This is particularly evident in remote work settings, where the boundary between professional and personal lives becomes increasingly blurred (Kumari, 2022; Komal et al., 2021). Men, on the other hand, are more likely to experience work-to-family conflict, often due to long hours, commuting stress, and workplace competitiveness (Hungund et al., 2024).

Overlaying these personal and social variables is the influence of work arrangements. Remote and hybrid models, while offering spatial and temporal flexibility, can also lead to role ambiguity, extended work hours, and emotional strain if not managed with clear boundaries (Ford et al., 2020; Yeves et al., 2022). Conversely, traditional on-site models offer structured environments and spatial separation, but may constrain autonomy, and elevate stress due to rigid schedules and travel demands (Palumbo, 2020).

Amidst these challenges, certain organizational factors, such as work autonomy and perceived organizational support emerge as protective resources. Employees with greater autonomy report lower work-family conflict, as they are better able to modify their schedules to accommodate personal needs (Mohammed et al., 2022). Similarly, informal flexibility and empathetic supervision have been found more effective than formal policy changes in reducing conflict (Allen et al., 2020; Chung and van der Lippe, 2020).

In addition to external supports, internal psychological resources also play a significant role in alleviating work-family conflict. Recent research highlights the buffering effects of

traits, such as self-compassion and gratitude, which help individuals regulate emotional responses, and build resilience against role strain (Tang et al., 2024). These internal mechanisms interact with organizational and social contexts, influencing how individuals cope with the dual demands of work and family.

In essence, the experience of work-family conflict emerges from a dynamic interplay of role expectations, organizational conditions, social norms, and individual coping strategies. Understanding this multifaceted construct within the context of Indian IT industry provides valuable insights into how contemporary work arrangements can be structured to promote both personal well-being and professional effectiveness.

Perceived Flexibility

In today's digitally connected and rapidly evolving work environments, especially in the organizations like Information Technology (IT), flexibility is no longer a perk; it is an essential feature of effective employment. Perceived flexibility refers to an employee's subjective experience of having autonomy over when, where, and how work is conducted, regardless of whether formal flexibility policies are in place (Allen et al., 2013; Hill et al., 2008). This construct highlights the psychological dimension of flexibility. It is not merely the presence of flexible arrangements, but how employees interpret and experience them within the context of their work and personal responsibilities.

In the Indian IT industry where extended work hours, projects spanning different time-zones, and round-the-clock connectivity are common, perceived flexibility becomes a pivotal factor in determining job satisfaction, work-life balance, and psychological well-being. Employees who feel empowered to structure their work around their personal needs are more likely to experience reduced stress, higher engagement, and stronger organizational commitment. However, perceived flexibility is a double-edged sword. When it is subtly

imposed as a requirement rather than offered as a choice, it can create pressure, uncertainty, and burnout.

Theoretical Framework Underpinning Perceived Flexibility

Boundary Theory:

The Boundary Theory formulated by Ashforth, Kreiner, and Fugate (2000) offers a relevant conceptual lens to understand perceived flexibility in the context of modern work arrangements. This theory posits that individuals actively manage the boundaries between work and non-work domains to maintain role clarity, psychological well-being, and performance. Boundaries can be either segmented (clearly separated) or integrated (blended), and the degree of flexibility one perceives is influenced by how easily these boundaries can be adjusted to accommodate shifting role demands.

Perceived flexibility aligns with boundary management preferences, which vary among individuals, and are shaped by factors, such as caregiving roles, job design, and organizational culture. Employees who favour boundary integration may view flexibility as empowering, whereas those who prefer segmentation may experience stress or role overload in flexible environments. This framework helps explain why the same flexible arrangement can produce vastly different psychological outcomes depending on individual coping strategies and situational variables. Moreover, it underscores the importance of boundary control — the ability to regulate when and how work intrudes into personal life — as a core psychological mechanism through which flexibility affects well-being and job satisfaction.

Correlates and Influencing Factors of Perceived Flexibility

Perceived flexibility is positively correlated with several beneficial outcomes, including job satisfaction, employee engagement, and productivity; and negatively associated with stress, work-family conflict, and emotional exhaustion (Kossek and Ozeki, 2018; Mahapatra and Dash, 2022). Employees with high levels of perceived flexibility often report a greater sense of control over their professional responsibilities, which supports smoother integration with demands of their personal lives. This is particularly relevant in hybrid and remote contexts, where work-life boundaries are often self-managed and fluid.

The experience of flexibility, however, varies significantly by gender. A growing body of research shows that women consistently report higher flexibility requirements than men, due to disproportionate caregiving responsibilities. Shockley and Shen (2020) reported that women in tech roles perceived flexibility not as a benefit, but as a necessity for managing overlapping domestic and professional roles. Similarly, De Menezes and Kelliher (2020) observed that women in the UK IT sector viewed flexibility as a crucial mechanism for sustaining career participation, while men were more likely to use it to enhance performance rather than balance.

A large-scale meta-analysis by Butts, Casper, and Yang (2019) affirm that women not only perceive a greater need for flexible arrangements but also benefit more from them, especially when organizations recognise and accommodate their unique challenges. Chung and van der Horst (2018) further confirmed these findings across European contexts, noting that caregiving roles significantly shaped how flexibility was both experienced and required, with women bearing a greater burden of adaptation.

The nature of work arrangements also plays a pivotal role in how flexibility is perceived. Remote workers tend to experience the highest levels of perceived flexibility, but also face elevated expectations of constant availability, role blurring, and emotional fatigue (Wang et al., 2021; Wontorczyk and Roznowski, 2022). On the other hand, employees in traditional on-site roles report lower perceived flexibility, but also lower pressure to be available beyond formal working hours, thus experiencing less psychological strain related to flexibility demands. Hybrid workers often benefit from moderate flexibility with fewer intrusions, making it a more balanced option for managing boundaries effectively (Gajendran et al., 2021).

Despite its benefits, perceived flexibility can become burdensome when it transforms into an implicit obligation. In such cases, employees feel compelled to adapt continually, respond after hours, and/or reschedule personal commitments to align with fluctuating work demands (Thomas and Höge, 2013; Soga et al., 2022). This phenomenon is particularly prevalent in the IT sector, where digital tools enable constant connectivity; and cultural expectations often equate availability with commitment. Hence, if not managed mindfully, flexibility may become a source of stress rather than relief, especially for women and remote employees, who face compounded pressures both at home and at work.

Moreover, organizational culture plays a critical role in shaping how flexibility is experienced. While formal policies may provide structural options, other factors, such as

managerial trust, peer norms, and informal accommodations ultimately determine whether flexibility is empowering or exploitative (Kelliher and Anderson, 2017). Mahapatra and Dash (2022) found that Indian IT professionals preferred hybrid models not merely for their structural benefits, but for the perceived balance they offer between autonomy and connectedness.

Finally, flexibility outcomes are shaped by individual coping mechanisms and personal resourcefulness. As Yeves et al. (2022) observed, flexibility enhanced well-being only when employees were able to regulate boundaries and disconnect when needed. Psychological skills, such as self-discipline, boundary-setting, and goal clarity help mitigate the risks of overwork and emotional fatigue, particularly in remote and hybrid contexts.

In essence, perceived flexibility is a complex and context-dependent construct that holds great potential for enhancing employee well-being, but only when implemented thoughtfully. Its positive impact hinges not just on structural work arrangements, but on supportive leadership, inclusive policies, and individual coping capabilities. Understanding how perceived flexibility operates, especially across gender and work models offers valuable direction for IT organizations striving to create adaptive, equitable, and sustainable workplaces.

Work Autonomy

In the evolving landscape of modern work, the concept of autonomy has emerged as a cornerstone of employee well-being, motivation, and performance. Work autonomy defined as the degree of discretion, control, and independence individuals have in scheduling their work, selecting methods, and making decisions (Hackman and Oldham, 1976), is increasingly recognised as a fundamental psychological need. It reflects the extent to which employees can exercise self-direction in the execution of tasks, thereby influencing their sense of ownership, competence, and intrinsic motivation at work.

This need for autonomy has become especially salient in the context of remote and hybrid work models, which have redefined traditional boundaries of supervision, scheduling, and task execution. In the Indian Information Technology (IT) sector, where knowledge work dominates, and performance is often output-driven, autonomy is not only desirable but also necessary for maintaining efficiency and engagement. However, the exercise of autonomy is deeply embedded in structural and cultural contexts, and its impact is shaped by factors, such as organizational design, technological infrastructure, managerial style, and individual competencies.

Theoretical Framework Underpinning Work Autonomy

Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model:

The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model, proposed by Demerouti et al. (2001) and expanded by Bakker and Demerouti (2007) provides a robust theoretical framework for understanding the role of work autonomy in shaping employee well-being and performance. According to the model, every job contains demands (e.g., workload, emotional pressure etc.) and resources (e.g., autonomy, feedback, support etc.). While demands can lead to strain and burnout, resources help buffer these effects and promote motivation and engagement.

Work autonomy is conceptualised in the JD-R model as a key job resource. When employees experience autonomy, they are more likely to feel intrinsically motivated and engaged, which in turn enhances their ability to manage job demands and sustain high performance. In environments where demands are high, as is often the case in IT roles, autonomy acts as a psychological buffer that fosters resilience and adaptive functioning.

Moreover, autonomy enhances the sense of ownership and personal accountability, which aligns with the model's assertion that job resources stimulate personal growth, learning, and goal attainment. The JD-R model thus supports the view that autonomy, especially when

supported by other organizational resources, contributes not only to individual well-being but also to overall organizational success.

Job Demands–Resources (JD–R) Model

Correlates and Influencing Factors of Work Autonomy

Work autonomy does not function in isolation; rather, it operates at the intersection of individual needs, organizational conditions, and socio-cultural dynamics. Empirical evidence suggests that work autonomy is positively correlated with job satisfaction, intrinsic motivation, work engagement, and task performance, while inversely associated with emotional exhaustion and disengagement (Wang et al., 2021; Santos et al., 2024). These outcomes are particularly salient in high-intensity sectors like IT, where innovation and problem-solving rely heavily on self-directed work.

The experience of autonomy is further shaped by gendered divisions of labour, and the domestic roles individuals occupy outside the workplace. Within the Indian context, women often bear a disproportionate share of household responsibilities, which can limit the perceived benefits of workplace autonomy. Even in flexible roles, sociocultural expectations may restrict

women's ability to exercise scheduling freedom to its fullest potential (Kotýnková Krotká, 2024). Men, while less encumbered by domestic obligations, may also experience autonomy pressures in performance-driven cultures that value constant availability.

Overlaid on the demographic factors is the influence of work arrangements. Employees working remotely or in hybrid setups generally report higher levels of autonomy than their on-site counterparts, given the increased flexibility in managing tasks and time (Chatterjee et al., 2022; Santos et al., 2024). This structural freedom, however, can be undermined by blurred boundaries, managerial ambiguity, and digital overexposure - factors that erode the motivational advantages autonomy typically provides (Wang et al., 2021). On-site workers, while less exposed to these ambiguities, often experience reduced control over their schedules and methods due to rigid institutional norms.

Amidst these complexities, organizational factors, such as perceived organizational support and leadership style emerge as key moderators. Research indicates that when autonomy is supported by empathetic leadership and a psychologically safe environment, it is more likely to translate into positive outcomes like reduced stress and enhanced engagement (Dewi and Salendu, 2023). Conversely, in unsupportive environments, autonomy may feel like abandonment leading to decision fatigue, techno-stress, or role overload (Toscano and Zappalà, 2020).

In addition to structural and interpersonal conditions, individual capacities also influence how autonomy is perceived and utilised. Employees with strong boundary management skills and digital self-regulation are more capable of leveraging autonomy for creative and efficient work. When paired with adequate guidance and trust, autonomy fosters not only productivity but also a sense of ownership and personal growth.

In essence, work autonomy is shaped by a complex interplay of job design, social expectations, organizational climate, and individual agency. In the dynamic and demanding

landscape of the Indian IT sector, a nuanced understanding of autonomy is essential, not merely as a structural provision, but as a psychologically enabling resource that, when supported, can lead to sustained well-being and high performance of the employees.

Job Performance

Job performance is a central construct in Organizational Psychology, broadly defined as the degree to which an employee effectively fulfils the responsibilities and tasks associated with his or her role (Campbell, 1990). It encompasses dimensions, including task performance, that is, execution of core duties, and contextual performance, that is, contributions beyond assigned tasks. In knowledge-intensive industries like Information Technology (IT), where outcomes often rely on cognitive labour, self-direction, and collaborative efficiency, job performance becomes an essential indicator of organizational success and employee fit.

The shift towards flexible work arrangements — remote, hybrid, and on-site — has transformed how performance is both experienced and evaluated. No longer confined to physical presence or rigid schedules, job performance today is shaped by a constellation of factors, including autonomy, managerial support, digital accessibility, and work-life integration. As the Indian IT industry adapts to these evolving structures, understanding how performance is impacted under various conditions becomes increasingly critical for sustaining productivity and employee well-being.

Theoretical Framework Underpinning Job Performance

Campbell's Model of Job Performance:

The conceptual understanding of job performance is strongly grounded in Campbell's Model of Job Performance (1990), which divides performance into multiple components, primarily task performance (the effectiveness with which core job duties are carried out) and contextual performance (the additional behaviours that contribute to the organizational environment, such as cooperation and initiative). This model highlights that performance is not

a singular trait but an outcome influenced by knowledge, skill, motivation, and situational variables.

Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model:

The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007) provides a complementary lens by positing that job performance is a product of balancing demands (e.g., workload, emotional strain) with resources (e.g., autonomy, managerial support, digital tools). Under flexible work arrangements like remote and hybrid models, this framework is especially relevant: when employees are given sufficient resources to manage demands, their performance tends to improve. Conversely, in the absence of such supports, performance may decline despite structural flexibility. The integration of Campbell's and JD-R models thus offers a comprehensive explanation of how individual competencies interact with organizational conditions to produce performance outcomes in evolving work contexts.

Correlates and Influencing Factors of Job Performance

Job performance is not a static trait but a dynamic outcome influenced by a complex set of personal, structural, and social variables. Studies done in the IT sector have consistently

shown that flexible work arrangements, particularly hybrid and remote models enhance performance when supported by enabling systems. Bloom et al. (2015) found a 13% increase in productivity among the remote workers in a randomized control trial, attributing the improvement to fewer breaks, reduced sick days, and increased focus. Similarly, Choudhury et al. (2021) highlighted that remote work enhanced output when paired with digital infrastructure and outcome-based evaluations.

In the Indian context, Kumar and Velmurugan (2022) reported that hybrid work models yielded higher perceived performance and satisfaction among IT employees compared to fully remote or on-site roles. These findings suggest that a mix of autonomy and in-person interaction may be optimal for knowledge workers, offering the benefits of flexibility without sacrificing collaboration. Singh and Sharma (2019) also emphasized that managerial support and trust were the critical moderators of performance in flexible settings.

Job performance is also contingent on individual adaptability and environmental factors. Toscano and Zappalà (2020) observed that while many remote employees reported stable or improved productivity, performance varied significantly based on factors like digital fatigue, home distractions, and emotional strain. This underscores the importance of considering the psychosocial conditions under which performance is evaluated.

Beyond structural and psychological conditions, gender-based differences add another layer of complexity. Research indicates that women often display lower task and contextual performance in remote settings, not due to skill deficits, but due to increased work-family conflict and caregiving responsibilities (Komal et al., 2021; Shockley et al., 2017). Vega et al. (2015) found that female teleworkers, despite having comparable technical competencies to their male counterparts, experienced more frequent home-based disruptions, contributing to variability in output. These findings align with broader concerns about gendered burdens in flexible work environments.

Work arrangements also influence the performance dynamics significantly. Hybrid workers consistently report high performance due to balanced interaction and autonomy (Choudhury et al., 2021). Remote employees often excel in individual technical tasks, but face challenges in team-based performance areas due to physical separation from the coworkers (Allen et al., 2015). On-site workers, particularly in rigid office settings, report higher stress and lower satisfaction, correlating with reduced overall performance metrics.

Furthermore, leadership style and organizational culture serve as important performance enablers. Contreras et al. (2020) noted that transformational leadership played a key role in sustaining remote work performance, particularly during periods of uncertainty or transition. Similarly, Prasad and Mishra (2021) highlighted the need for a multi-dimensional performance assessment including adaptive, task, and contextual domains, to capture the full impact of flexible work arrangements.

In essence, job performance is shaped by a dynamic interplay of work conditions, support systems, personal circumstances, and gendered responsibilities. While remote and hybrid arrangements offer structural advantages, their effectiveness depends on leadership, technological infrastructure, and employees' capacity to manage multiple roles.

Perceived Organizational Support (POS)

Perceived Organizational Support (POS) refers to employees' beliefs about the extent to which their organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being (Eisenberger et al., 1986). As a psychological construct, perceived organizational support plays a vital role in shaping employees' attitudes, motivation, and behaviours. In contemporary knowledge-based sectors like Information Technology (IT), where employees often work in distributed and digitally mediated environments perceived organizational support has become especially significant. It not only affects how employees engage with their work, but also determines their sense of inclusion, trust, and loyalty toward the organization.

With the widespread adoption of flexible work arrangements including remote, hybrid, and on-site models, perceived organizational support has gained renewed relevance. The physical and relational distance created by virtual work can potentially weaken employees' emotional connection to their organization. Consequently, how support is communicated, perceived, and internalized becomes a critical determinant of job satisfaction, engagement, and performance outcomes.

Theoretical Framework Underpinning Perceived Organizational Support

Organizational Support Theory (OST):

The foundation for understanding perceived organizational support lies in Organizational Support Theory (OST), proposed by Eisenberger et al. (1986). This theory states that employees form global beliefs concerning how much the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being. These perceptions are shaped through repeated interactions and cues, such as recognition, supervisor support, and fairness that signal the organization's commitment to the employee.

According to OST, high levels of perceived support enhance employees' sense of obligation to reciprocate through increased affective commitment, organizational citizenship behaviour, and job performance. Conversely, low levels of support can lead to withdrawal, disengagement, and turnover intentions. The theory further asserts that perceived organizational support satisfies socioemotional needs, such as esteem, belonging, and approval, which are especially relevant in remote and hybrid work settings where face-to-face interactions are limited.

In the context of flexible work arrangements in the Indian IT sector, OST provides a useful lens to understand how virtual communication, leadership style, and inclusive practices influence employees' emotional connection to the organization. It highlights that how support

is perceived is as critical as the support itself, reinforcing the need for organizations to actively cultivate trust, recognition, and consistent communication in digitally mediated environments.

Correlates and Influencing Factors of Perceived Organizational Support

Perceived Organizational Support (POS) is shaped by a complex interaction of individual perceptions, organizational practices, and broader cultural influences. At the individual level, employees who perceive strong support from their organizations tend to report higher job satisfaction, increased engagement, and better psychological well-being (Showkat et al., 2020; Sihag, 2021). This is especially relevant in the IT sector, where flexible work arrangements have become more common, and employees face challenges related to physical distance, communication barriers, and role ambiguity. In remote and hybrid work settings, perceived organizational support serves as a crucial psychological resource reducing feelings of isolation, and reinforcing trust and alignment with organizational values (Rajeswari and Venugopal, 2024). Indian IT employees working in hybrid models have been found to report better work-life balance and lower stress when they perceive their organizations as supportive, as this helps them manage the shifting boundaries between work and personal life (Kumar and

Sarkar, 2023). Similarly, the remote workers show higher motivation and lower turnover intentions when organizational support is demonstrated through consistent communication, recognition, and accessible leadership (Showkat et al., 2020; Dhar, 2012).

The nature of perceived organizational support also intersects with gendered experiences in the workplace. Research indicates that male employees often perceive greater organizational support compared to their female counterparts, a disparity linked to cultural norms and structural biases that affect how support is delivered and experienced (Al-Taie and Khattak, 2024). Women tend to value relational aspects of support more deeply, emphasizing interpersonal connection and empathy, whereas men more frequently focus on tangible rewards, such as promotions and pay (Pocztowski and Urbaniak, 2023). This heightened sensitivity to support or its absence can significantly impact women's engagement and well-being, particularly in male-dominated or hierarchical organizational cultures common in the Indian IT sector (Agarwal, 2016; Kurtessis et al., 2017). Female employees in organizations with limited communication or impersonal managerial practices have reported lower levels of engagement when perceived organizational support is perceived as weak.

Work arrangements further complicate the experience of organizational support. Remote employees often report lower levels of perceived organizational support due to reduced informal interactions, and less immediate feedback from supervisors (Zito et al., 2021). In contrast, hybrid workers tend to perceive the highest levels of support, as the blend of in-person and virtual contact fosters a greater sense of inclusion and belonging (Jung et al., 2021). Research suggests that well-structured virtual communication and frequent supervisory engagement can bridge the support gap experienced by remote employees, emphasizing that how support is communicated is as critical as its content (Yuhjung and Youngkeun, 2021). These findings underline the importance of adaptable organizational practices that respond to the specific needs of different work arrangements.

In essence, perceived organizational support is a dynamic construct influenced by personal expectations, gendered experiences, managerial behaviours, and the structural realities of work models. As hybrid and remote work modes become integral to the Indian IT industry, fostering perceived organizational support through inclusive leadership, proactive communication and empathetic recognition will be vital. Such efforts can enhance employee well-being, increase engagement, reduce turnover, and ultimately build a resilient and motivated workforce despite physical and temporal distances.

It is essential to examine how different work arrangements shape employees' experiences of work-family conflict, flexibility, autonomy, job performance, and perceived organizational support. Understanding these relationships within the Indian IT sector addresses a critical gap in existing research while offering practical insights for organizations aiming to optimise work models in a rapidly evolving environment. Accordingly, this research investigates the combined effects of work arrangements and gender on a few key psychological factors, with the goal of advancing both theoretical knowledge and organizational practice.

CHAPTER 2
REVIEW OF
LITERATURE

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The evolving landscape of work arrangements—particularly the rise of hybrid and remote models—has reshaped traditional organizational structures and employee experiences. Within the Indian IT sector, known for its dynamic and demanding environment, these shifts have raised critical questions about how different modes of working impact employee attitude and performance. The following review focuses on the existing body of research to contextualize the present study, which investigates some of the psychological outcomes associated with on-site, hybrid, and remote work arrangements. The review emphasizes key constructs including work-family conflict, perceived flexibility requirements, work autonomy, job performance, and perceived organizational support, offering a structured understanding of how these variables interact with varying work formats.

Work-Family Conflict

Work-family conflict (WFC) refers to the tension that arises when the demands of work and family roles are mutually incompatible, such that participation in one role hampers the fulfilment of the other (Greenhaus and Beutell, 1985). In high-demand sectors like Information Technology (IT) where employees often operate under intense pressure and time-bound conditions, this conflict is especially pronounced. The emergence of varied work arrangements, that is, remote, hybrid, and on-site has further diversified how work-family conflict is experienced. Additionally, social roles assigned to men and women outside the workplace influence the nature of this conflict, making sex a critical dimension of analysis.

Comparison based on Gender

Hungund, Gujanal, and Suresh (2024), in a study of 179 IT professionals in Bengaluru, found that women being supported by stronger time management and support systems reported better work-life balance than men. In contrast, men experienced higher work-to-family conflict

due to peer pressure, long commutes, and workload. The study challenges traditional assumptions and highlights the sexed nature of work-family conflict in IT settings.

Thriveni Kumari (2022), in a study of 392 IT professionals across India, found that work-family conflict more negatively impacted women's career advancement than men's. Female employees cited domestic responsibilities as barriers to leadership roles, while men were less affected. The study underscores how sexed expectations and unequal workloads hinder women's professional growth in the IT sector.

Deshwal, Gupta, and Kararha (2021) in a study of 100 remote-working employees in India, examined sex differences in work-family conflict and its impact on job performance. The results showed that female employees experienced significantly higher levels of work-family conflict compared to their male counterparts. The findings indicate how remote mode of work may amplify sexed challenges in balancing professional and domestic roles, particularly for women.

Shockley et al. (2017) analysed data from 1,027 U.S. employees, comprising 512 men and 515 women across various industries, including IT, to explore sex differences in work-family conflict and job performance. Results found women reporting significantly higher levels of work-family conflict than men. The researchers suggested that work-family conflict, particularly prevalent among women, played a critical role in shaping job performance outcomes.

Comparison based on Work Arrangement

Apart from sex, the nature of work arrangement significantly shapes the intensity and form of work-family conflict. Sharma and Sharma (2024) investigated the causes and consequences of work-family conflict in a study of 366 IT employees in India working under hybrid arrangements. Their findings revealed that blurred boundaries, extended work hours, and lack of a dedicated workspace at home were significant stressors for the employees. Those factors

collectively contributed to elevated levels of work-family conflict, with employees reporting challenges in balancing their personal and professional responsibilities.

Santos et al. (2024) examined 545 software employees in a South American IT firm, and reported that hybrid work models were generally perceived positively, particularly when aligned with employee preferences and team workflows. The study highlighted that autonomy in choosing work location enhanced satisfaction and balance, suggesting hybrid arrangements as a potentially optimal structure.

Khanna et al. (2024) conducted a multi-country analysis of 124 software companies, and found that hybrid models contributed to improved individual productivity and organizational efficiency. However, they noted that team cohesion and spontaneous collaboration sometimes suffered in distributed work environments, indicating the need for structured communication strategies.

Mankar, Katare, and Anjum (2023) made a study on the IT professionals in Coimbatore, India, and emphasized that flexible working conditions, especially hybrid models helped reduce work-life conflict when paired with supportive organizational policies. Their findings revealed that balancing employee autonomy with clear expectations played a key role in fostering a healthier work-life interface.

Vattapparambath (2023) conducted a study with 100 IT employees from Info Park - a prominent information technology park located in Kochi, Kerala, India, and found that while work-from-home (WFH) arrangements improved flexibility, they also led to challenges, such as blurred work-life boundaries and increased emotional strain. In contrast, traditional work-from-office (WFO) setups were associated with commuting stress and rigid schedules, but offered clearer separation between work and personal life.

Christy et al. (2021) studied 75 women IT professionals in Bangalore, and found a strong preference for work-from-home due to greater flexibility and reduced commuting, which

supported better work-life balance. However, challenges like extended hours and home distractions were noted. In contrast, office work offered structure but increased work-family conflict due to inflexible schedules. The findings suggest that flexible work models may better support women's work-life integration in the IT sector.

In a broader context, Ford et al. (2020) surveyed 3,634 software developers globally during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study revealed that remote work increased scheduling flexibility, but introduced challenges like social isolation, reduced informal learning opportunities, and difficulty separating work and personal responsibilities, especially among those with caregiving roles.

In essence, Sex and work arrangements influence work-family conflict. Most of the researches conducted so far have indicated that women face more family-to-work conflict, while men experience more work-to-family conflict. Hybrid set-ups ease both types of conflict by combining flexibility with structure; however, their effectiveness is context-dependent, varying according to factors like job demands, organizational policies, availability of a dedicated workspace at home, and individual time-management abilities.

Perceived Flexibility Requirements

Perceived flexibility requirements refer to the extent to which employees feel expected to be adaptable to work demands outside formal hours or locations (Thomas and Höge, 2013). In digitally connected work environments, including the IT sector, flexibility is often transformed from a resource into an obligation. Employees may feel compelled to respond beyond work hours, reschedule personal commitments, or manage inconsistent workloads. These perceived demands are shaped by both sex and the nature of work arrangements.

Comparison based on Gender

Shockley and Shen (2020) studied 300 employees in the U.S. technology and professional sectors, and reported sex differences in flexibility requirements. Women indicated significantly

higher flexibility requirements, driven by the need to juggle overlapping domestic responsibilities alongside work tasks. Men, on the other hand, tended to use flexibility mainly as a tool to enhance work-related autonomy, experiencing fewer conflicting demands.

In another UK based study of 250 IT professionals, equally divided by sex, De Menezes and Kelliher (2020) observed that female employees required more flexibility to balance their professional and family roles. Conversely, male IT professionals viewed flexibility more as a mean to improve their individual performances rather than as a necessity for managing work-family boundaries.

A comprehensive review by Kossek et al. (2019) synthesized empirical evidence across various industries, reinforcing that women have a greater perceived need for work-life flexibility compared to men. The review highlighted how traditional sex roles continue to shape flexibility requirements, influencing women's experiences more heavily in balancing work and family.

Butts, Casper and Yang (2019) conducted a meta-analysis covering over 100 studies focusing on employees from multiple sectors, including IT. The findings showed that women not only perceived higher flexibility requirements but also derived greater benefits from flexible work policies than men, emphasizing the critical role of such policies in supporting sexed work-life challenges.

Chung and van der Horst (2018) after analysing large-scale survey data from over 4,000 European employees found that women consistently reported higher perceived needs for flexible work arrangements than men. The disparity was largely attributed to women's greater caregiving responsibilities, which heightened their demand for flexibility to manage both domestic and professional roles effectively.

Comparison based on Work Arrangement

Work arrangements significantly influence how flexibility is interpreted, either as empowering or burdensome. Wontorczyk and Roznowski (2022), in a comparative study of 321 employees from Polish organizations, investigated perceived flexibility under different work models, namely, remote, hybrid, and on-site. Their findings revealed that the remote workers reported the highest perceived flexibility requirements, often driven by blurred boundaries and expectations of constant availability. The Hybrid employees experienced moderate flexibility demands, benefiting from some control over their schedules. In contrast, the on-site workers reported the lowest perceived flexibility requirements, largely due to the structured and predictable nature of their work environment.

Gajendran, Harrison, and Delaney-Klinger (2021) further contributed to this literature by examining 400 IT and knowledge workers in the U.S., focusing on telecommuting versus hybrid and on-site models. They found that the workers on hybrid mode experienced lower perceived flexibility strain and better boundary management than fully remote or on-site employees.

A cross-national study by Wang, Liu, and Parker (2021), involving 270 employees (120 from India and 150 from the UK), reinforced these patterns. The Indian remote workers, especially women reported greater pressure to extend work hours, and manage cross-time zone coordination than their counterparts. The study concluded that when flexibility is framed as an implicit requirement rather than a voluntary benefit, it becomes a stressor, particularly for the employees managing responsibilities in both personal and professional spheres.

In essence, these findings highlight that perceived flexibility demands impact employee well-being, especially the women in remote and hybrid roles. True flexibility requires active support from organizational culture and policies, which is also crucial for the organizations aiming for equity and sustainability.

Work Autonomy

Work autonomy refers to the degree of control employees have over how, when, and where they complete their tasks (Breugh, 1985). In the context of modern work arrangements, autonomy has gained even more attention, as digital tools have allowed for greater decentralization and self-management. However, autonomy is not experienced uniformly; it often intersects with both sex and the nature of work arrangements, particularly in knowledge-intensive fields like the IT sector.

Comparison based on Gender

Chung and van der Horst (2018) analysed longitudinal panel data collected from the UK Household Longitudinal Study, covering over 10,000 employees. The researchers found that while both men and women reported access to flexible working options, women, especially mothers were less able to translate this into actual control over work schedules. This was largely due to caregiving responsibilities and organizational expectations. The findings highlighted that formal autonomy does not necessarily equate to experienced autonomy.

Kossek and Lautsch (2018) synthesized evidence from multiple industries and roles through a meta-analytic and conceptual review. They introduced the concept of “bounded flexibility” where workers, particularly women in lower-status roles, had access to flexible arrangements in theory but not in practice. Their findings emphasized that autonomy was influenced not only by job type but also by informal norms, managerial attitudes, and social expectations, limiting actual autonomy for many women.

Craig and Brown (2017) used time-use data from 4,500 Australian dual-earner couples to examine autonomy and childcare. Mothers experienced more work interruptions and less schedule control, while fathers better leveraged flexible hours. The study highlighted that autonomy was mediated by sex roles, with women’s autonomy often compromised by household expectations.

Comparison based on Work Arrangement

Rai and Ghosh (2022) surveyed 360 IT professionals across Hyderabad, Pune, and Noida in India to examine perceived autonomy under three work arrangements, namely, remote, hybrid, and on-site. The study found that the remote employees reported the highest levels of autonomy, particularly in scheduling and task execution. The hybrid workers experienced moderate level of autonomy, while the on-site employees reported the lowest, largely due to increased supervision and rigid routines. The findings affirmed that work arrangement type significantly influenced perceived autonomy in the Indian IT sector.

Ono (2022) conducted qualitative interviews with 30 Japanese white-collar employees during the Covid-19 pandemic, to explore how remote work impacted autonomy and productivity of the employees. The employees in firms that used output-based performance evaluation systems and supported telework infrastructure reported increased autonomy in managing tasks and communications. However, disparities in digital skills and lack of managerial trust limited those benefits for some workers. The study emphasizes that remote work does not automatically ensure autonomy; supportive cultures and technology are crucial.

A deeper perspective was offered in a longitudinal study by Zhou et al. (2020), which included IT professionals from India and China. In this study of 400 participants, the researchers tracked autonomy perceptions across changing work models during the Covid-19 pandemic. While autonomy increased significantly for remote and hybrid employees during lockdown periods, it declined over time for women, especially those who lacked dedicated home-office spaces or had caregiving responsibilities. The study emphasized that work autonomy was not just a matter of work mode but also of domestic context and managerial expectations.

Bloom et al. (2015) conducted a nine-month randomized controlled trial involving 249 employees of a Chinese travel agency (Ctrip). The participants were randomly assigned to work

from home and work at office modes. Those in the remote group reported higher autonomy in task scheduling and location flexibility, as well as a 13% performance increase. However, the increased autonomy also required stronger self-regulation, as employees assumed more responsibility for managing their output.

In essence, Work autonomy is shaped by both sex and work arrangements. Men, especially in remote roles benefit more, while women face competing demands. Hybrid roles offer balance, but true autonomy requires trust, supportive policies, and equity.

Job Performance

Job performance is generally defined as the level of effectiveness with which employees perform their tasks and responsibilities (Campbell, 1990). Job performance can be influenced by a range of factors including personal attributes, motivation, job satisfaction, and work environment. The dynamics of sex and work arrangements (on-site, hybrid and remote) further complicate and shape employees' job performance, especially in the context of the rapidly evolving IT sector.

Comparison based on Gender

Deshwal, Gupta, and Kararha (2021) based on their study of 100 remote-working employees in India reported negative correlation between work-family conflict and job performance, particularly in task and contextual domains. Male participants were found to score higher in both areas than females. However, no sex difference was observed in counterproductive work behaviours.

Shockley et al. (2017) reported a similar finding. The researchers analysed data from 1,027 male and female U.S. employees across various industries, to study the impact of work-family. The elevated conflict among women was found to correlate negatively with both task and contextual performances among them, while no significant sex differences emerged for counterproductive behaviours.

Vega, Anderson, and Kaplan (2015) conducted a study with 219 employees from various sectors including IT, working in remote and on-site setups in the United States. The research focused on individual differences including sex, and how telework affected job performance. Findings showed that although men and women had comparable technical competencies, female employees experienced more frequent disruptions to their work due to home responsibilities, leading to greater variability in performance. The study emphasized that women's job performance was influenced not only by workplace demands but also by the uneven distribution of domestic duties, particularly in remote and hybrid contexts.

Comparison based on Work Arrangement

Work arrangements are known to have a significant impact on employees' ability to perform. Kumar and Velmurugan (2022) examined the job performance of IT professionals across hybrid, remote, and on-site arrangements. Based on a survey of 420 employees from prominent IT firms in India, the researchers reported that hybrid work models resulted in higher perceived job performance and job satisfaction compared to fully on-site or remote setups.

In another survey of 1,200 knowledge workers, including IT employees, across the United States, Choudhury, Foroughi and Larson (2021) compared job performance among remote, hybrid, and on-site workers. The sample included 400 employees from each work arrangement category. The hybrid workers were observed to exhibit a balanced and often superior performance profile, excelling both in individual technical tasks and collaborative team settings. The remote workers scored the highest on individual task performance, but reported challenges in teamwork and innovation due to physical separation from the actual workplace and the coworkers. The on-site workers, especially in traditional office environments, faced higher stress levels and reported lower job satisfaction than their counterparts from the other categories, which correlated with their reduced performance metrics.

Allen, Golden, and Shockley (2015) performed a meta-analysis of 46 studies on telecommuting, involving over 12,000 participants across multiple sectors, including IT, and found that remote workers consistently reported higher job performance compared to their on-site counterparts. The key contributors to this enhanced performance were increased autonomy, fewer workplace distractions, and the ability to customize work environments. Remote employees benefited from flexible scheduling and the elimination of commuting time, factors that collectively led to improved task completion and productivity.

In essence, job performance has been shaped by sex and work arrangements. Men often report higher performance influenced by fewer work-life conflicts and workplace biases. Hybrid and remote roles enhance performance through greater flexibility and autonomy, while rigid on-site setups may hinder it. Supportive and flexible policies help boost performance across all groups.

Perceived Organizational Support (POS)

Perceived Organizational Support (POS) refers to employees' beliefs regarding the degree to which their organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being (Eisenberger et al., 1986). As a key indicator of how supported employees feel, perceived organizational support also helps explain variations in employee experiences across different work arrangements and sexes. Remote, hybrid, and on-site settings, along with individual needs, can shape how support is perceived, making POS especially relevant in understanding diverse workplace dynamics.

Comparison based on Gender

A recent study by Al-Taie and Khattak (2024) examined the relationship between perceived organizational support, high-commitment human resource practices, and innovative work behaviour among academic staff in the United Arab Emirates. The findings indicated a significant sex-based disparity in perceived organizational support. Male employees perceived

higher levels of support from their organizations compared to their female counterparts. This disparity was further reflected in work outcomes, with men demonstrating a stronger positive association between perceived organizational support and innovative behaviour. The researchers suggested that underlying cultural and structural factors might influence how support was both extended and perceived across sexes in formal institutions.

In 2023, Poczowski and Urbaniak investigated sex differences in organizational commitment in a Polish national sample, incorporating perceived organizational support as one of the key drivers. Although overall levels of commitment across sex were found to be statistically similar, the underlying contributors varied. Women reportedly placed greater importance on interpersonal relationships and supportive work environments, the dimensions closely aligned with perceived organizational support, while men prioritized tangible career outcomes, such as promotion and compensation. The findings highlight that even when commitment levels appear comparable, the pathways through which perceived organizational support affect men and women may diverge due to different expectations from organizational support systems.

In a meta-analytic evaluation, Kurtessis et al. (2017) integrated findings from over 300 studies across diverse industries, including knowledge-based work environments, and observed that sex moderated the relationship between perceived organizational support and the key work outcomes. Specifically, women were more sensitive to variations in perceived organizational support. The study revealed that female employees often perceived less organizational investment in their well-being, particularly in male-dominated or hierarchically rigid sectors, which aligned with patterns observed in parts of the Indian IT sector.

Agarwal (2016) examined the relationship between perceived organizational support and work engagement among 312 employees in the Indian IT industry, with a specific focus on sex differences. The female participants reported significantly lower work engagement when

perceived organizational support was perceived to be weak, especially in environments where managerial communication was infrequent or lacked personal relevance. Agarwal emphasized that inclusive recognition practices, transparent communication, and active feedback mechanisms were essential to enhance perceived organizational support among the female employees. The findings highlighted the importance of tailoring organizational support strategies to address sex-specific needs and promote equitable workplace engagement.

Comparison based on Work Arrangement

The nature of work arrangements also impacts how employees perceive organizational support. In a comprehensive study by Zito et al. (2021) involving Italian employees working under remote and in-office arrangements during the Covid-19 pandemic, it was found that the remote workers perceived significantly lower organizational support than their on-site counterparts. This reduction in perceived support was attributed to limited informal interactions, reduced face-to-face managerial contact, and a diminished sense of inclusion in organizational culture. The authors emphasized that digital communication often lacked the warmth and immediacy required to foster emotional support and organizational attachment.

Similarly, Jung et al. (2021) examined a U.S. based sample of knowledge workers, and stated that remote employees experienced a sharp decline in perceived organizational support when organizational communication was infrequent or impersonal. However, those in hybrid roles alternating between remote and in-person work demonstrated the highest levels of perceived organizational support. The study concluded that hybrid work models offered a unique advantage, that is, the employees retained autonomy while still engaging in periodic face-to-face interactions that reinforced their connections to the organizations. Hybrid arrangements also enabled spontaneous feedback and inclusion in informal networks, which were also the key predictors of perceived organizational support.

Following a cross-cultural perspective, Yuhjung and Youngkeun (2021) conducted a study on the South Korean IT professionals, and revealed that fully on-site workers perceived organizational support the most, largely due to regular supervisory engagement and access to in-house resources. However, the gap in perceived organizational support between remote and on-site workers significantly narrowed in organizations that implemented structured virtual communication and recognition systems. The findings point out to the critical role of managerial practices in maintaining high level of perceived organizational support, regardless of physical location of the worker.

In a nutshell, perceived organizational support (POS) is one of the key factors in employee engagement and retention, with sex and work arrangements moderating the relationship. Women, in hybrid or remote roles often feel less supported, but recognition and feedback from the supervisors can help. Remote workers perceive the lowest level of support, while hybrid roles offer more balance. Inclusive practices and regular communication are essential to make employees feel valued, irrespective of sex and work arrangement.

Overall, the reviewed literature highlights the growing significance of flexible work arrangements in shaping key psychological outcomes for employees. While hybrid and remote models have demonstrated benefits in terms of autonomy, performance, and work-life balance, inconsistencies across sex and experience levels indicate the need for deeper investigation of the area. These insights provide a foundation for identifying critical gaps and informing the direction of future research.

Research gaps

While the existing literature offers valuable insights into the psychological and operational implications of varied work arrangements, several critical research gaps persist, particularly within the Indian IT sector. Much of the existing finding is rooted in Western contexts, with limited empirical studies capturing the cultural, structural, and technological nuances of India's

rapidly evolving digital workforce. This creates a significant contextual void, especially given the widespread adoption of hybrid and remote work models in Indian IT organizations since the Covid-19 pandemic.

Another limitation noted is the fragmentation of psychological variables across separate studies. Most investigations have focused on singular constructs, such as work-family conflict (Netemeyer et al., 1996), job performance (Rupietta and Beckmann, 2018), or work autonomy (Morgeson et al., 2006), rarely examining how these variables may coexist or interact within the same model. This siloed approach limits holistic understanding of how different psychological dimensions, such as autonomy, flexibility demands, organizational support, and performance—operate simultaneously under different work arrangements.

Another notable gap lies in the lack of direct, quantitative comparisons among remote, hybrid, and on-site work formats using standardized psychological constructs. While some studies have examined remote or hybrid work individually (Bloom et al., 2015; Oakman et al., 2022), very few offer comparative analysis across all three work arrangements within a single study. This weakens the empirical foundation for developing tailored, evidence-based organizational policies responsive to the psychological impacts of each work model.

A particularly underexplored area is that of perceived flexibility requirements — the implicit or explicit pressure employees feel to remain constantly adaptable and available. Although flexibility is often conceptualized as a resource or benefit, available literature (Thomas and Höge, 2019; Gerich, 2021) suggests that, it can also function as a demand that contributes to increased stress and work-family interference. This nuanced distinction remains conceptually and empirically neglected, especially in the Indian IT sector, where organizational expectations and workplace norms frequently encourage employees to be available beyond regular working hours, blurring the boundaries between work and personal life.

Moreover, demographic variables, such as sex and work experience are frequently overlooked in studies examining work arrangements. Despite a growing focus on inclusive workplace practices, few studies have so far explored how these variables might mediate or moderate the psychological impacts of hybrid, remote, or on-site work arrangements. This omission limits understanding of how men and women, especially early-career professionals may experience autonomy, support, flexibility pressures, and performance expectations differently.

Finally, current research tends to generalize IT employees without accounting for differences in roles or experience levels. Role-specific demands, such as project deadlines, client coordination, or team-based coding may significantly alter how work arrangements are perceived and experienced. Although the present study does not focus on job roles per se, it controls for work experience by accounting for differences in years of professional exposure, as work experience can influence how employees perceive and manage psychological variables like work-family conflict and job performance. The analysis is also stratified across distinct work models to derive more nuanced and context-sensitive interpretations. In a nutshell, the present study seeks to address the gaps in previous researches by examining the impact of different work arrangements, that is, on-site, hybrid, and remote on a set of psychological variables including work-family conflict, perceived flexibility requirements, work autonomy, job performance, and perceived organizational support among Indian IT professionals in the early stages of their careers. Through integrative, comparative analysis and consideration of sex and work experience, this research offers a holistic and contextually grounded understanding of modern work arrangements within a critical segment of the Indian workforce.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

METHODOLOGY

3.1) Title of the Present Study:

A Comparative Study of Work-Family Conflict, Perceived Flexibility Requirement, Work Autonomy, Job Performance and Perceived Organizational Support among Indian IT Employees across Sex and Work Arrangement

3.2) Objectives of the Present Study:

The present study aims to compare a sample of IT employees of India in respect of five psychological constructs, namely, work-family conflict, perceived flexibility requirements, work autonomy, job performance, and perceived organisational support based on sex and work arrangement.

The specific objectives may be outlined as follows:

1. To study whether male and female IT employees differ in respect of work-family conflict and its dimensions, namely, work-family conflict and family-work conflict.
2. To study whether male and female IT employees differ in respect of perceived flexibility requirements and its dimensions, namely, task fulfilment, career development, learning, and working time.
3. To study whether male and female IT employees differ in respect of work autonomy and its dimensions, namely, work method autonomy, work scheduling autonomy, and work criteria autonomy.
4. To study whether male and female IT employees differ in respect of job performance and its dimensions, namely, task performance and contextual performance.
5. To study whether male and female IT employees differ in respect of perceived organisational support.

6. To study whether IT employees working in different work arrangements, namely, on-site, hybrid, and remote differ in respect of work-family conflict and its dimensions, namely, work-family conflict and family-work conflict.
7. To study whether IT employees working in different work arrangements, namely, on-site, hybrid, and remote differ in respect of perceived flexibility requirements and its dimensions, namely, task fulfilment, career development, learning, and working time.
8. To study whether IT employees working in different work arrangements, namely, on-site, hybrid, and remote differ in respect of work autonomy and its dimensions, namely, work method autonomy, work scheduling autonomy, and work criteria autonomy.
9. To study whether IT employees working in different work arrangements, namely, on-site, hybrid, and remote differ in respect of job performance and its dimensions, namely, task performance and contextual performance.
10. To study whether IT employees working in different work arrangements, namely, on-site, hybrid, and remote differ in respect of perceived organisational support.

3.3) Operationalization of concepts:

- **Work-Family Conflict**

Work-family conflict (WFC) is defined as a form of inter-role conflict where demands from work and family domains are mutually incompatible, such that participation in one role makes it difficult to fulfil the other (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985). It operates in two directions: work interfering with family (WIF) and family interfering with work (FIW), each with distinct but often overlapping effects (Frone et al., 1992). In essence, WFC captures the bidirectional strain between professional and personal roles.

In the context of the Indian IT sector, where professionals often face long hours, tight deadlines, and blurred work-life boundaries, WFC is a pertinent concern. While flexible work arrangements are increasingly implemented to improve work-life balance, their effectiveness

may vary depending on how such flexibility is structured and perceived. As noted by Chung (2020), flexibility that is employer-oriented or poorly implemented may inadvertently intensify work-family conflict.

To assess both directions of work-family conflict—work interfering with family (WIF) and family interfering with work (FIW)—the Netemeyer, Boles, and McMurrian (1996) scale is employed, offering a balanced measure of how professional and personal demands may clash. This operationalization allows for a nuanced understanding of how distinct work arrangements influence employees' capacity to manage work-life boundaries.

- **Perceived Flexibility**

Perceived flexibility requirements refer to the extent to which employees feel they must be available or adaptable beyond formal hours or routines to meet organizational demands (Thomas & Hornung, 2013).

Perceived flexibility requirements refer to the implicit pressure on employees to stay adaptable and available beyond formal hours, often blurring work-life boundaries (Thomas & Hornung, 2013). Research highlights the difference between flexibility as a personal resource and as an organizational demand that adds strain. Terms like "invisible flexibility" and "adaptive burden" describe these often-unspoken expectations, especially in remote or digital work settings.

Thomas and Hornung (2013) conceptualize flexibility requirements as a dual-edged construct—offering autonomy in theory, yet frequently serving as a vehicle for intensifying work demands. In hybrid and remote work settings, this tension becomes more evident, as flexibility is no longer a matter of choice but an assumed norm. In this context, perceived flexibility requirements reflect not just structural changes in work arrangements but the psychological toll of constantly negotiating boundaries between personal and professional life.

- **Work Autonomy**

Work autonomy refers to the degree to which individuals have control over how, when, and in what order they complete their job tasks (Breugh, 1985). It is a core component of job design, and is closely tied to employee motivation, job satisfaction, and overall performance. Autonomy enables employees to exercise discretion in decision-making and planning, contributing to a sense of ownership and engagement at work. In essence, work autonomy is a multidimensional construct that captures an individual's perceived control over various aspects of their work.

With the rise of remote and hybrid work environments, autonomy has become increasingly significant in shaping employee outcomes. To measure this construct, the established scale by Breugh (1985) is applied to assess employees perceived autonomy across different work arrangements.

- **Job Performance**

Job performance is a multidimensional construct that refers to how well an individual executes tasks and responsibilities associated with his or her job role. It typically encompasses two broad dimensions: task performance, which includes the core duties outlined in a job description, and contextual performance, which includes behaviours that support the social and psychological environment of the organization (Çalışkan & Köroğlu, 2019). In essence, job performance reflects both the tangible completion of work and the employee's broader contribution to organizational culture.

Job performance in the IT sector is closely linked to work-life dynamics, with flexibility and role-related stressors significantly impacting employee output and efficiency. Empirical findings highlight that work-life flexibility can enhance performance, while work-family conflict may reduce it (Prasad & Mishra; Siddiqui, 2021). Additionally, job performance is

influenced by psychological factors such as well-being and recovery, which are supported by flexible and hybrid work arrangements (Rieder, 2022).

Performance will be assessed through a multidimensional framework that captures both task execution and contextual behaviours, reflecting the influences of contemporary work arrangements in the IT industry.

- **Perceived Organizational Support**

Perceived Organizational Support (POS) refers to employees' general belief that the organization values their contributions, and cares about their well-being (Eisenberger et al., 1986). Rooted in organizational support theory, POS emerged from the understanding that when employees feel supported, they reciprocate through increased loyalty, engagement, and performance (Eisenberger & Huntington, 1986). In essence, POS reflects the psychological safety and trust an organization provides its employees.

Research indicates that in flexible work arrangements, POS plays a critical role in influencing employee motivation, job performance, and retention (Kaur & Arora, 2023). This construct thus provides a framework for examining the relationship between organizational care and employee outcomes.

3.4) Hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of work-family conflict.

Hypothesis 1a: Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of work-to-family conflict dimension of work-family conflict.

Hypothesis 1b: Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of family-to-work conflict dimension of work-family conflict.

Hypothesis 2: Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 2a: Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of task fulfilment dimension of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 2b: Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of career development dimension of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 2c: Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of learning dimension of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 2d: Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of working time dimension of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 3: Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of work autonomy.

Hypothesis 3a: Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of work method autonomy dimension of work autonomy.

Hypothesis 3b: Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of work scheduling autonomy dimension of work autonomy.

Hypothesis 3c: Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of work criteria autonomy dimension of work autonomy.

Hypothesis 4: Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of job performance.

Hypothesis 4a: Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of task performance dimension of job performance.

Hypothesis 4b: Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of contextual performance dimension of job performance.

Hypothesis 5: Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of perceived organisational support.

Hypothesis 6: IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of work-family conflict.

Hypothesis 6a: IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of work-to-family conflict dimension of work-family conflict.

Hypothesis 6b: IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of family-to-work conflict dimension of work-family conflict.

Hypothesis 7: IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 7a: IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of task fulfilment dimension of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 7b: IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of career development dimension of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 7c: IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of learning dimension of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 7d: IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of working time dimension of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 8: IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of work autonomy.

Hypothesis 8a: IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of work method autonomy dimension of work autonomy.

Hypothesis 8b: IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of work scheduling autonomy dimension of work autonomy.

Hypothesis 8c: IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of work criteria autonomy dimension of work autonomy.

Hypothesis 9: IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of job performance.

Hypothesis 9a: IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of task performance dimension of job performance.

Hypothesis 9b: IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of contextual performance dimension of job performance.

Hypothesis 10: IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of perceived organisational support.

Hypothesis 11: IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work-family conflict.

Hypothesis 11a: IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work-to-family conflict dimension of work-family conflict.

Hypothesis 11b: IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of family-to-work conflict dimension of work-family conflict.

Hypothesis 12: IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 12a: IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of task fulfilment dimension of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 12b: IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of career development dimension of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 12c: IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of learning dimension of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 12d: IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of working time dimension of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 13: IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work autonomy.

Hypothesis 13a: IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work method autonomy dimension of work autonomy.

Hypothesis 13b: IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work scheduling autonomy dimension of work autonomy.

Hypothesis 13c: IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work criteria autonomy dimension of work autonomy.

Hypothesis 14: IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of job performance.

Hypothesis 14a: IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of task performance dimension of job performance.

Hypothesis 14b: IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of contextual performance dimension of job performance.

Hypothesis 15: IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of perceived organisational support.

Hypothesis 16: IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work-family conflict.

Hypothesis 16a: IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work-to-family conflict dimension of work-family conflict.

Hypothesis 16b: IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of family-to-work conflict dimension of work-family conflict.

Hypothesis 17: IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 17a: IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ

significantly in respect of task fulfilment dimension of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 17b: IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of career development dimension of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 17c: IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of learning dimension of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 17d: IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of working time dimension of perceived flexibility requirements.

Hypothesis 18: IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work autonomy.

Hypothesis 18a: IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work method autonomy dimension of work autonomy.

Hypothesis 18b: IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work scheduling autonomy dimension of work autonomy.

Hypothesis 18c: IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work criteria autonomy dimension of work autonomy.

Hypothesis 19: IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of job performance.

Hypothesis 19a: IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of task performance dimension of job performance.

Hypothesis 19b: IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of contextual performance dimension of job performance.

Hypothesis 20: IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of perceived organisational support.

3.5) Tools used in the study:

To verify the hypotheses the following tools were used:

- General Information Schedule developed by the present investigator
- Work-Family Conflict Scale (Netemeyer, Boles, and McMurrian, 1996)
- Perceived Flexibility Requirements (PFR) Scale (Höge and Hornung, 2015)
- Work Autonomy Scale (James A. Breugh, 1985)
- Job Performance Scale (Çalışkan and Köroğlu 2022)
- Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS) – 8-item version (Eisenberger, Huntington, Hutchison, and Sowa, 1986)

General Information Schedule:

The General Information Schedule developed by the present investigator has been designed to collect relevant background information from the participants to contextualize their responses to the main variables under the study. The Schedule is organized into four broad sections: Demographic Information, Job Details, Work Arrangement Details, and Family and Household Details.

Demographic Information

This section contains basic demographic data, including age, gender, and highest educational qualification of the participants.

Job Details

This section contains items concerning the participants' current job roles, designations/the level of their positions within the organization, total length of work experience in the IT sector, duration of their service in the present IT organizations, and their current work locations.

Work Arrangement Details

This section focuses on understanding the nature and structure of the participants' current work arrangements. The items include the current work model (remote, on-site, or hybrid), the

duration for which they have been working in this arrangement, the mode of work specific to their present organizations, and whether their job involve overtime or not. For the hybrid arrangement, additional item, such as the number of days per week for remote and on-site work is included.

Family and Household Details

To gain insight into the participants' personal environments, this section consists of items related to marital status, whether the participant has children or not, the number of children, whether the spouse is employed or not, and whether the participant is the sole earning member of the household or not.

Work-Family Conflict Scale

The Work-Family Conflict Scale developed by Richard G. Netemeyer, James S. Boles, and Robert McMurrian (1996) are designed to assess the bidirectional interference between work and family roles. Specifically, the Work-to-Family Conflict (WFC) dimension captures the extent to which work demands interfere with family responsibilities, whereas the Family-to-Work Conflict (FWC) dimension evaluates how family demands hinder work-related tasks. Each dimension comprises five items, resulting in a total of ten items. Although the original scale used a 7-point Likert format, in the present study, the items were adapted to a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Higher average scores on each subscale indicate greater levels of conflict in the respective direction.

The scale has demonstrated high internal consistency across multiple samples. In the original validation study, Cronbach's alpha coefficients were reported as 0.88 for the Work-Family Conflict (WFC) scale and 0.86 for the Family-Work Conflict (FWC) scale. These values reflect strong internal consistency in the initial validation. Additionally, further applications of the scale have yielded reliability estimates of $\alpha = 0.91$ for WFC and $\alpha = 0.84$ for FWC, supporting its broader psychometric robustness.

Construct validity has been supported through significant correlations with related constructs. Both WFC and FWC were positively associated with job tension, burnout, and depression. WFC also correlated positively with job role conflict and ambiguity, while FWC showed significant associations with reduced self-efficacy and lower sales performance. Discriminant validity was established through moderate inter-correlations between WFC and FWC ($r = 0.33$), suggesting the two constructs are related but distinct. Additionally, negative correlations with job satisfaction, life satisfaction, and organizational commitment, along with positive correlations with turnover intentions, further support the construct validity of the scales.

Perceived Flexibility Requirements (PFR) Scale

The Perceived Flexibility Requirements (PFR) Scale, developed by Thomas Höge and Severin Hornung (2015) measures employees' perceptions of organizational expectations for flexibility across various aspects of their roles. The scale is designed to capture how much flexibility individuals feel is required of them by their organization in order to succeed and contribute effectively. The original version of the PFR Scale consists of 13 items and is divided into four subscales, namely, Task Fulfilment, Career Development, Learning, and Working Time.

- The Task Fulfilment dimension containing 4 items reflects expectations around adapting and adjusting tasks to align with organizational needs.
- The Career Development dimension consisting of 3 items focuses on the need to remain flexible in one's career progression, and to embrace emerging development opportunities.
- The Learning dimension having 3 items addresses adaptability in acquiring new skills and knowledge.

- The Working Time dimension comprising 3 items evaluates the perceived necessity of being flexible with working hours and schedules.

The responses are recorded on a 6-point Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree). Scores for each dimension are derived by averaging the responses to their respective items, with higher scores indicating greater perceived organizational expectations for flexibility in that area.

The scale has demonstrated satisfactory internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients of 0.76 for Task Fulfilment, 0.85 for Career Development, 0.76 for Learning, and 0.76 for Working Time dimensions. The validity of the PFR Scale is further supported by significant canonical correlations between its subdimensions and proactive work orientations, such as the need for efficiency (ranging from 0.24 to 0.39) and the need for challenge (ranging from 0.14 to 0.32). These results suggest that individuals perceiving higher flexibility demands tend to display stronger proactive attitudes at work.

Work Autonomy Scale

The Work Autonomy Scale, developed by James A. Breugh in 1985, is designed to measure the degree of autonomy employees experience in performing their job roles. The scale assesses three distinct dimensions of work autonomy, namely, Work Method Autonomy, Work Scheduling Autonomy, and Work Criteria Autonomy. Each dimension is measured using three items, totalling 9 items in the full scale.

- Work Method Autonomy refers to the extent to which employees can independently determine the methods, procedures, and techniques used to carry out their tasks.
- Work Scheduling Autonomy captures the level of control employees have over the timing and sequencing of their work activities.
- Work Criteria Autonomy reflects the degree of freedom employees possess in setting the standards or benchmarks by which their job performance is evaluated.

The responses are recorded using a 7-point Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 7 (Strongly Agree). Scores for each subscale are computed by averaging responses to the three corresponding items, with higher scores indicating a greater perceived level of autonomy in that specific domain.

The scale has demonstrated acceptable levels of internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients reported as 0.68 for Work Method Autonomy, 0.79 for Work Scheduling Autonomy, and 0.69 for Work Criteria Autonomy domains. Confirmatory factor analysis has supported the three-factor structure, thereby validating the theoretical distinctions among the dimensions. Additionally, the scale has exhibited construct validity through meaningful correlations with related job characteristics. For instance, positive correlations are observed with job satisfaction, job involvement, organizational commitment, and employee participation in decision-making processes, confirming that higher autonomy is linked with more favourable work attitudes and behaviours.

Job Performance Scale

The Job Performance Scale, developed by Abdullah Çalışkan and Özlem Köroğlu in 2022, is a psychometric instrument intended to measure employee performance across two key dimensions, namely, Task Performance and Contextual Performance. This scale has been specifically constructed to reflect the dual aspects of performance in modern organizational settings—one that captures not only the core job tasks but also the broader behavioural contributions employees make to the workplace.

- Task Performance refers to how effectively an individual carries out duties that are directly related to the organization's technical functions.
- Contextual Performance assesses discretionary behaviours that contribute to the organizational environment, such as cooperating with colleagues, demonstrating initiative, and adhering to workplace norms and policies.

The scale comprises 11 items, with 5 items measuring Task Performance and 6 items addressing Contextual Performance. The respondents are required to rate each item using a 5-point Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). The scores are computed by summing the responses for each sub-dimension, with higher scores indicating better perceived performance in the respective areas.

The scale has demonstrated strong internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients reported as 0.871 for university staff, 0.914 for healthcare professionals, and 0.943 for industrial sector employees. The Task Performance subscale demonstrated a Cronbach's alpha of 0.85, reflecting high internal consistency, likely due to the cohesive nature of items measuring core job functions. In contrast, the Contextual Performance subscale yielded a slightly lower alpha of 0.78, which remains acceptable but reflects the broader and more diverse range of discretionary behaviours it assesses.

Construct validity has been confirmed through both Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), which support the two-factor model aligning with task and contextual performances. Criterion validity has further been supported through significant positive correlations with job satisfaction, suggesting that employees with higher performance scores also report higher levels of satisfaction.

Perceived Organizational Support (POS) Scale – 8-item version

The Perceived Organizational Support (POS) Scale, originally developed by Robert Eisenberger, Robin Huntington, Steven Hutchison, and Deborah Sowa in 1986, is a widely used instrument designed to assess employees' perceptions of how much the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being. The 8-item version of the scale is a unidimensional measure that captures perceived organizational support as a single, overarching construct, while maintaining the core elements of the original 36-item scale.

The respondents indicate their agreement with each item on a 7-point Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 7 (Strongly Agree). The overall POS score is calculated by reverse-coding negatively worded items and averaging responses across all 8 items. Higher scores reflect greater perceived support from the organization.

Among the 8 items, several are negatively worded to minimize response bias and encourage thoughtful engagement with each statement. These negatively phrased items must be reverse-coded before analysis. Specifically, if a participant selects a 1 (Strongly Disagree) on a negatively worded item, it would be converted to a 7, a 2 becomes a 6, and so on, using the formula: $\text{Reversed score} = 8 - \text{Original score}$.

The short version has been shown to retain excellent psychometric properties. The 8-item version of the scale consistently reports alpha coefficients above 0.85, indicating strong internal consistency.

Construct validity has been supported through significant correlations with related constructs, such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and turnover intentions. Similarly, criterion validity has been demonstrated by the scale's ability to predict key employee outcomes, including higher job performance, lower turnover rates, and stronger commitment to the organization. The POS scale has been employed across a wide range of industries including manufacturing, service, retail, and technology sectors, highlighting its broad applicability and robustness.

3.6) Study area and sample:

The present sample comprised employees working in the Software and IT Services Sector across India, representing a diverse range of technical and professional roles including software engineers, developers, data analysts, consultants, and project managers. The employees actively engaged in three different work arrangements, namely on-site, hybrid, and

remote were selected, forming the basis for a comparative analysis of relevant psychological and job-related variables.

Data collection was conducted entirely through online modes, with participants being contacted via various social media platforms, such as WhatsApp, Instagram, and LinkedIn, as well as through email and professional networks. This approach facilitated the inclusion of IT employees from major technology hubs across India, including Bangalore, Hyderabad, Pune, Gurugram, and other cities known for their significant IT workforce.

The final sample consisted of 154 IT employees, distributed across the three work arrangements as follows:

- On-site: 50 employees (27 males and 23 females)
- Hybrid: 54 employees (29 males and 25 females)
- Remote: 50 employees (23 males and 27 females)

Among the participants, 79 were male and 75 were female employees.

Purposive sampling was considered appropriate for this study, as it allowed deliberate inclusion of the participants who could best provide insights relevant to the research objectives, ensuring representation across different work arrangements, and professional roles within the Information Technology sector.

The samples were selected based on the following pre-determined criteria:

Selection Criteria

- The respondents must be full-time employees currently working in the Information Technology (IT) and Software Services sector in India.
- Only those working in specific departments related to software engineering, software development, data analytics, IT consulting, quality assurance, project and product management, system engineering, cybersecurity, DevOps, cloud services, and user

interface/user experience (UI/UX) development and related technical roles must be considered as the respondents.

- The respondents must have been working under one of the specified work arrangements (on-site, hybrid and remote) for a minimum of one year to ensure adequate exposure to the respective work mode.
- Only those with a minimum of one year of total work experience in the IT Software sector must be considered.
- Employees working in overseas offices or outside India should not be included.
- The respondents were to be selected irrespective of age and sex; however, only Indian citizens must be included to maintain demographic relevance.
- Participation must be voluntary, and only those who provided informed consent should be considered for the study.

3.7) Administration of the Tools:

Data for the present study were collected exclusively through an online mode to ensure wide reach and accessibility among the IT employees across India. The survey was done through the administration of a Google Form, which incorporated the informed consent form and a set of psychological scales, namely, Work-Family Conflict and Family-Work Conflict Scale (Netemeyer, Boles, & McMurrin, 1996), Perceived Flexibility Requirements (PFR) Scale (Höge & Hornung, 2015), Work Autonomy Scale (Breaugh, 1985), Job Performance Scale (Çalışkan & Köroğlu, 2022), and the 8-item Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS) (Eisenberger, Huntington, Hutchison, & Sowa, 1986) along with the General Information Schedule (developed by the present investigator).

Prior to sharing the online survey link, potential participants were contacted through various social media platforms, including WhatsApp, Instagram, and LinkedIn. They were clearly communicated about the purpose of the present study, and were also assured that the

information shared by them would be kept confidential and would solely be used for academic purpose. Afterwards, the consents of the willing participants were obtained via text messages. The first page of the Google Form presented an overview of the study's aims along with a detailed informed consent statement. The participants could proceed to the next section only after providing their explicit consents. The eligibility criteria were enforced by including screening questions in the General Information Schedule, ensuring that only the IT employees with a minimum of one year of work experience could participate. All the items of the questionnaires were marked mandatory, to prevent participants from skipping any question. The participants could move forward only after responding to all the items of a particular section or questionnaire.

Throughout the process, the investigator ensured that all collected data were kept confidential and were used exclusively for academic and research purposes.

3.8) Scoring and Tabulation:

After collection, the data were tabulated and scored accordingly. In case of the General Information Schedule, the frequencies of all the items were determined after tabulating the data in respect of the participants' sex, namely, male and female. In case of other questionnaires, namely, the Work-Family Conflict and Family-Work Conflict Scale, Perceived Flexibility Requirements Scale, Work Autonomy Scale, Job Performance Scale, and Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS) – 8-item version, respective scoring keys were used to score the data. Tabulation work was done separately for each scale in respect of sex and work arrangement.

3.9) Statistical Analysis of Data:

To depict a typical picture of the general characteristic features of the participants, descriptive statistics like mode and percentage were calculated. The Mode was computed for the items like age, current job role or position, years of experience in the IT sector, years of

work experience in the present organization, number of days worked from home and on-site (for employees placed under hybrid mode), duration of current work arrangement in the present organisation, and number of children (if applicable). Percentages were calculated to for variables, such as sex, educational qualification, designation or level, work location, current work arrangement, overtime involvement, marital status, presence of children, spouse's employment status, and sole earning status (financial responsibility within the family).

Furthermore, mean and standard deviation were calculated for each category of the selected respondents, based on gender and work arrangement (on-site, remote, and hybrid), in respect of the psychological constructs assessed in the study, namely, work-family conflict, perceived flexibility requirement, work autonomy, job performance, and perceived organizational support.

Thereafter, t-tests were used to compare the respondents based on gender and work arrangement on account of work-family conflict and its dimensions, namely, work-to-family conflict and family-to-work conflict (FWC); perceived flexibility requirement and its dimensions, namely, task fulfilment, career development, learning, and working time; work autonomy and its dimensions, namely, work method autonomy, work scheduling autonomy, and work criteria autonomy; job performance and its dimensions, namely, task performance, and contextual performance; and perceived organisational support.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1) Results:

Table 1 depicts the general characteristics of the present sample of IT employees working under different work arrangements, namely, on-site, hybrid, and remote, in different organizations located across India, in respect of several demographic variables.

Table 1: General Characteristics of the Respondents

General Characteristics of Sample (N = 154)	Values
Age of participant in years (Mode Value)	26
Sex (%)	
Male	51.3
Female	48.7
Educational Qualification (%)	
Graduate	79.9
Post Graduate	16.9
Diploma in IT/related fields	2.6
Others	0.6
Current Job Role / Position (%)	
Software Development & Engineering	42.2
Data Science & Analytics	25.3
UI/UX & Design	2.0
IT Infrastructure & DevOps	7.1
IT Consulting & Business	15.6
IT Support & Entry-Level	5.8
IT Operations / Logistics Tech	2.0
Designation / Level (%)	
Entry-Level	21.8
Junior Associate	23.8
Mid-Level	36.9
Senior-Level	5.2
Manager/Team Lead	3.2
Director/VP	0
Consultant	4.5
Freelancer/Contractor	3.3
Others	1.3

Years of Experience in the IT Sector (Mode Value)	4
Years of Experience in the present IT organization (Mode Value)	2
Current Work Location (%)	
Andhra Pradesh	0.6
Arunachal Pradesh	0
Assam	0
Bihar	2.0
Chhattisgarh	0.6
Goa	1.3
Gujarat	0.6
Haryana	5.8
Himachal Pradesh	0
Jharkhand	2.6
Karnataka	11.7
Kerala	3.9
Madhya Pradesh	0.6
Maharashtra	16.2
Manipur	0
Meghalaya	0
Mizoram	0
Nagaland	0
Odisha	1.3
Punjab	2.0
Rajasthan	0
Sikkim	0
Tamil Nadu	2.0
Telangana	1.4
Tripura	0
Uttar Pradesh	4.5
Uttarakhand	0
West Bengal	36.4
Andaman and Nicobar Islands	0
Chandigarh	0
Dadra and Nagar Haveli and Daman and Diu	0
Lakshadweep	0
Delhi	6.5
Puducherry	0
Jammu and Kashmir	0
Ladakh	0
Current Work Arrangement (%)	
On-Site (Full-time office work)	32.5
	35.1

Hybrid (Combination of on-site and remote work) Remote / Work from Home	32.4
[In Hybrid] Number of Days of Work from Home per Week (Mode Value)	2
[If Hybrid] Number of Days of Work on-site per Week (Mode Value)	3
Duration of current work arrangement in the present organization (Mode Value)	1 year
Overtime Involvement (%) Yes No	46.1 53.9
Marital Status (%) Single Married Divorced Widowed Prefer not to say	93.5 4.5 0 0 2.0
Parent of Children (%) Yes No	99.4 0.6
Number of Children, (if applicable) (Mode Value)	0
Spouse's Employment Status (%) Yes No Not Applicable	3.9 2.6 93.5
Sole Earning Member of the Family (%) Yes No	11 89

According to Table 1, the modal age of the respondents is 26 years. The sample consists of almost equal numbers of male and female IT employees, with a slightly higher representation of male employees (51.3%) compared to females (48.7%). In terms of educational background, most of the participants (approximately 80%) are graduates, while 17% hold a postgraduate degree. A small fraction of the sample (2.6%) possesses diplomas in IT or related fields, and less than 1% have Ph.D. degree. The most commonly reported job role among the participants is that of a Software Development and Engineering (42.2%). Regarding job designation, around 22% of the respondents

are employed at entry-level positions, while 24% are junior associates. Mid-level professionals constitute about 37% of the sample, and smaller proportions of the respondents are playing the roles of senior-level executives (5.2%), manager or team lead (3.2%), consultant (4.5%), and freelancer/contractor (3.2%). None of the participants has reported holding director or VP-level role. The modal values for overall experience in the IT sector and experience in the current organization are four years and two years respectively, suggesting that a substantial proportion of the sample have progressed beyond entry-level roles, but are still in the early to mid-stages of their careers. The respondents represent a wide geographical spread, with the highest concentration in West Bengal (36.4%), followed by Delhi (6.5%), Maharashtra (16.2%), and Karnataka (11.7%). Smaller representations are noted from the states like Haryana (5.8%), Kerala (3.9%), and Bihar (2%). Participants from other Indian states and union territories made up minimal percentages, with many states showing negligible or no representation in the sample.

Regarding the work arrangements, almost equal representations from on-site (32.5%), hybrid (35.1%), and remote (32.5%) work modes are evident in the present sample. Among those in hybrid roles, the most common pattern is working from home for two days and from the office for three days per week. The typical duration of the current work arrangement is found to be one year.

In terms of overtime involvement, 46% of the participants have reported about working beyond regular hours, while 54% have not engaged in overtime work. In so far as the marital status of the participants is concerned, a large majority of the respondents (94%) are found to be single, and only 4.5% have reported being married. A negligible portion have preferred not to disclose their marital status. Interestingly, almost all respondents (99.4%) do not have children.

Regarding family-related employment variables, majority of respondents (93.5%) indicated that the question of spouse's employment status was not applicable to them. Of those for whom it was applicable, 3.9% reported that their spouse was employed, while 2.6% reported otherwise. 11%

of the participants had reported being the sole earners in their households, while the remaining 89% did not bear the sole financial responsibility of their families.

Fig 1a: Diagram representing the Distribution of Respondents based on Sex

Fig 1b: Diagram representing the Educational Qualification of Respondents

Fig 1c: Diagram representing the Distribution of Respondents by Designation/Level

Fig 1d: Diagram representing the distribution of Respondents based on Work Locations

Fig 1e: Diagram representing the Distribution of Respondents based on Work Arrangement

Fig 1g: Diagram representing the Distribution of Respondents based on Marital Status

Fig 1i: Diagram representing the Distribution of Respondents based on Earning Status**Table 2: Work-Family Conflict Scores of Male and Female IT Employees and Their Comparisons**

Work-Family Conflict Dimensions	Male (N=79)		Female (N=75)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
Work-to-family Conflict	3.1443	.98394	3.0933	0.88613	0.337*
Family-to-Work Conflict	2.4405	.92950	2.4960	0.83851	0.388*
Total	2.7924	.82629	2.7947	0.68515	0.018*

High score indicates high level of work family conflict

*Difference not significant

Table 2 presents the comparison between male and female IT employees with regard to their scores on different dimensions of the Work-Family Conflict Scale. The findings indicate that the two groups of participants have not differed significantly in both the parameters of work-family conflict, namely, Work-to-Family Conflict, Family-to-Work Conflict, and in respect of overall

Work-Family Conflict score. Therefore, Hypothesis 1, that is, “Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of work-family conflict,” is accepted. Moreover, Hypothesis 1a, stating that “Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of work-to-family conflict dimension of work-family conflict,” and Hypothesis 1b, stating that “Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of family-to-work conflict dimension of work-family conflict,” are both accepted.

Table 2 further reveals that the male IT employees have been observed to experience slightly higher levels of work-to-family conflict than their female counterparts, as reflected in their mean score, suggesting a marginally greater interference of professional responsibilities with family life. Notably, both groups scored slightly above the scale midpoint, indicating a moderate level of work-to-family conflict. Conversely, female employees have reported a marginally higher level of family-to-work conflict, implying that family obligations may somewhat more frequently impact their work roles. The mean scores for both groups in this dimension fall below the midpoint, denoting a generally low level of family-to-work conflict. Overall, the total work-family conflict scores are nearly identical and just below the midpoint, indicating that both groups experience a moderately low level of overall work-family conflict, highlighting a balanced management of work and family demands.

Fig 2: Diagram representing Work-Family Conflict Scores of Male and Female IT Employees**Table 3: Work-Family Conflict Scores of IT Employees on Hybrid and On-site Modes and their comparisons**

Work-Family Conflict Dimensions	Hybrid (N=54)		On-site (N=50)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
Work-to-family Conflict	3.1741	.94533	3.2360	0.91133	0.340*
Family-to-Work Conflict	2.4333	.95779	2.4280	0.75702	0.031*
Total	2.8037	.80046	2.8320	0.64569	0.197*

High score indicates high level of work family conflict

*Difference not significant

Table 3 presents the comparison between IT employees working under Hybrid and Onsite modes on different dimensions of the Work-Family Conflict Scale, namely, Work-to-Family Conflict, and Family-to-Work Conflict, and the total Work-Family Conflict score. The results show no statistically significant differences between the said two groups of employees, in respect of the dimensions as well as total scale. Therefore, Hypothesis 6, that is, "IT employees working under

on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of work-family conflict,” Hypothesis 6a, that is, “IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of work-to-family conflict dimension of work-family conflict,” and Hypothesis 6b, that is, “IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of family-to-work conflict dimension of work-family conflict,” are accepted.

Table 3 further reveals that employees working in a hybrid arrangement have experienced slightly lower levels of work-to-family conflict compared to their on-site counterparts, as reflected in the respective mean scores. This suggests that hybrid employees may face fewer disruptions in their family lives due to work-related responsibilities. Both groups scored above the scale midpoint, indicating a moderately high level of work-to-family conflict, with on-site workers showing slightly higher interference. With regard to family-to-work conflict, the scores for both groups are nearly identical and fall below the midpoint, reflecting a generally low level of interference of family responsibilities with work tasks. The total work-family conflict scores are also quite close, both lying just under the midpoint, signifying a moderately low overall experience of conflict across work arrangements. These findings point to minimal practical differences in the extent of work-family conflict between hybrid and on-site IT employees.

Fig 3: Diagram representing Work-Family Conflict Scores of IT Employees under Hybrid and On-site Modes

Table 4: Work-Family Conflict Scores of IT Employees on Hybrid and Remote Modes and their comparisons

Work-Family Conflict Dimensions	Hybrid (N=54)		Remote (N=50)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
Work-to-family Conflict	3.1741	.94533	2.9440	0.93986	1.244*
Family-to-Work Conflict	2.4333	.95779	2.5440	0.93025	0.597*
Total	2.8037	.80046	2.7440	0.82565	0.374*

High score indicates high level of work family conflict

*Difference not significant

Table 4 presents a comparative analysis of IT employees working under Hybrid and Remote modes based on their average scores on the Work-Family Conflict Scale, covering the dimensions of Work-to-Family Conflict, Family-to-Work Conflict, and the overall Work-Family Conflict. The findings indicate that there are no statistically significant differences between the two groups across

any of the dimensions. Accordingly, Hypothesis 16, which states that, “IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work-family conflict”, Hypothesis 16a, which states that “IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work-to-family conflict dimension of work-family conflict,” and Hypothesis 16b, which states that “IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of family-to-work conflict dimension of work-family conflict.” are accepted.

Table 4 further indicates that employees working in hybrid mode have experienced slightly higher levels of work-to-family conflict compared to their remote counterparts, reflecting a marginally greater intrusion of work responsibilities into personal life. The mean score for hybrid employees lies above the scale midpoint, suggesting a moderately high level of conflict, while that of remote workers falls just below it, indicating a moderate-to-low level. In contrast, remote employees have reported slightly more family-to-work conflict than those working in hybrid mode, implying a marginally stronger impact of family responsibilities on their professional roles. Both groups scored below the midpoint in this dimension, indicating a generally low level of family-to-work conflict. The total work-family conflict scores for both groups also fall just under the midpoint, pointing to a moderately low overall level of conflict and highlighting minimal differences between hybrid and remote work arrangements.

Fig 4: Diagram representing Work-Family Conflict Scores of IT Employees under Hybrid and Remote Modes

Table 5: Work-Family Conflict Scores of IT Employees working under On-site and Remote Modes and their Comparisons

Work-Family Conflict dimensions	On-site (N=50)		Remote (N=50)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
Work-to-family Conflict	3.2360	0.91133	2.944	0.93986	1.577*
Family-to-Work Conflict	2.4280	0.75702	2.544	0.93025	0.684*
Total	2.8320	0.64569	2.744	0.82565	0.594*

High score indicates high level of work family conflict

*Difference not significant

Table 5 displays the comparison between IT employees working under Onsite and Remote modes in respect of their scores on the Work-Family Conflict Scale. The results indicate that there are no statistically significant differences between the two groups across any of the dimensions assessed, namely, Work-to-Family Conflict, and Family-to-Work Conflict, as well as regarding the overall Work-Family Conflict. In view of these findings, Hypothesis 11, which states that “IT

employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work-family conflict,” is accepted. Furthermore, the dimension-specific hypotheses, that is, Hypothesis 11a, which states that “IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work-to-family conflict dimension of work-family conflict,” and Hypothesis 11b, which states that “IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of family-to-work conflict dimension of work-family conflict” are also accepted.

Table 5 further indicates that on-site employees experienced slightly higher levels of work-to-family conflict than their remote counterparts, pointing to a marginally greater spillover of work responsibilities into personal life. The mean score for the on-site group lies above the scale midpoint, suggesting a moderately high level of conflict, whereas the remote group’s mean falls just below the midpoint, reflecting a moderate-to-low level. In contrast, remote employees reported slightly higher family-to-work conflict, indicating that their family obligations may interfere with work roles to a slightly greater extent. Both groups scored below the midpoint in this dimension, signifying generally low levels of family-to-work conflict. Overall, the total work-family conflict scores are comparable and fall just under the midpoint, indicating moderately low levels of overall conflict and only minimal variation between the two work arrangements.

Fig 5: Diagram representing Work-Family Conflict Scores of IT Employees under On-site and Remote Modes

Table 6: Perceived Flexibility Requirement Scores of Male and Female IT Employees and their Comparisons

Perceived Flexibility Requirement dimensions	Male (N=79)		Female (N=75)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
Task Fulfilment	4.1291	1.02484	3.9680	0.93695	1.017*
Career Development	4.4051	1.23017	4.2467	1.16356	0.820*
Learning	4.0380	1.25006	3.9667	1.13404	0.370*
Working Time	3.9873	1.28159	3.9633	0.93604	0.133*
Total	4.1139	0.81695	4.0092	0.70467	0.850*

High score indicates high level of perceived flexibility requirements

*Difference not significant

Table 6 presents the comparison between male and female IT employees with respect to their scores in the Perceived Flexibility Requirement Scale. The findings indicate that there is no statistically significant sex-based difference across any of the dimensions, namely, task fulfilment,

career development, learning, and working time or the overall scale. Consequently, Hypothesis 2, which states that “Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of perceived flexibility requirements,” is accepted. In addition, the dimension-specific hypotheses, that is, Hypothesis 2a, which states that “Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of task fulfilment dimension of perceived flexibility requirements”, Hypothesis 2b, which states that “Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of career development dimension of perceived flexibility requirements”, Hypothesis 2c, which states that “Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of learning dimension of perceived flexibility requirements”, and Hypothesis 2d, which states that “Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of working time dimension of perceived flexibility requirements” are also accepted, based on the present findings.

It is further revealed from Table 6 that male IT employees have obtained slightly higher average scores than their female counterparts across all dimensions and the overall scale, indicating that men may perceive a marginally greater organizational expectation for flexibility in various aspects of their roles. In the Task Fulfilment and Career Development dimensions, both groups scored well above the midpoint, reflecting a strong perceived need for flexibility in executing tasks and pursuing long-term professional growth. The Career Development dimension, in particular, showed the most noticeable difference, suggesting that male employees may feel a slightly stronger need to adapt for career advancement. A similar pattern is evident in the Learning and Working Time dimensions, where both groups again scored above the midpoint, denoting a high perceived requirement for flexibility related to continuous learning and schedule management. Overall, the total scores for both male and female employees exceed the midpoint, indicating a generally high level of perceived flexibility requirement, with only minor variations observed between the sexes.

Fig 6: Diagram representing Perceived Flexibility Requirement Scores of Male and Female IT Employees

Table 7: Perceived Flexibility Requirement Scores of IT Employees working under Hybrid and On-site Modes and their Comparisons

Perceived Flexibility Requirement dimensions	Hybrid (N=54)		On-site (N=50)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
Task Fulfilment	4.1222	0.92709	4.0880	0.87520	0.193*
Career Development	4.3148	1.14223	4.5300	1.10384	0.976*
Learning	4.0648	1.22877	4.0500	1.05100	0.066*
Working Time	4.0417	1.20313	3.9300	1.07029	0.499*
Total	4.1182	0.73017	4.1015	0.68458	0.120*

High score indicates high level of perceived flexibility requirements

*Difference not significant

Table 7 depicts the comparison between the IT employees working under hybrid and on-site work arrangements in respect of their perceived flexibility requirement scores. It is evident from the

findings that the two groups of employees do not differ significantly regarding any of the dimensions of the scale, namely, Task Fulfilment, Career Development, Learning, and Working Time. Moreover, the difference between the said groups of respondents in terms of the total score is also found to be statistically insignificant. The findings lead towards acceptance of Hypothesis 7, that is, “IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of perceived flexibility requirements”, Hypothesis 7a, that is, “IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of task fulfilment dimension of perceived flexibility requirements”, Hypothesis 7b, that is, “IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of career development dimension of perceived flexibility requirements”, Hypothesis 7c, that is, “IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of learning dimension of perceived flexibility requirements”, and Hypothesis 7d, that is, “IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of working time dimension of perceived flexibility requirements”.

Table 7 further shows that while overall perceived flexibility requirements are similar across hybrid and on-site work modes, subtle variations are visible across specific dimensions. In the Task Fulfilment and Career Development dimensions, both groups scored above the midpoint, indicating a high perceived requirement for flexibility in managing tasks and supporting long-term career growth. On-site employees reported slightly higher scores in career development, suggesting a marginally greater emphasis on flexible pathways for advancement. Conversely, hybrid workers showed a slight edge in the Working Time dimension, implying a stronger preference for schedule adaptability within the hybrid structure. Scores in Learning and Working Time dimensions also exceeded the midpoint across both groups, reflecting high perceived needs for flexibility in skill-building and time management. Overall, the total perceived flexibility requirement scores for both work modes remain above the midpoint, denoting a consistently high level of perceived flexibility expectations, irrespective of work arrangement.

Fig 7: Diagram representing Perceived Flexibility Requirement Scores of IT Employees under Hybrid and On-site Modes

Table 8: Perceived Flexibility Requirement Scores of IT Employees working under Hybrid and Remote Modes and their Comparisons

Perceived Flexibility Requirement dimensions	Hybrid (N=54)		Remote (N=50)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
Task Fulfilment	4.1222	0.92709	3.9360	1.14103	0.916*
Career Development	4.3148	1.14223	4.1400	1.32880	0.721*
Learning	4.0648	1.22877	3.8900	1.29477	0.706*
Working Time	4.0417	1.20313	3.9500	1.10426	0.404*
Total	4.1182	0.73017	3.9646	0.87225	0.976*

High score indicates high level of perceived flexibility requirements

*Difference not significant

Table 8 presents the comparison between the IT employees working under hybrid and remote work arrangements, based on their perceived flexibility requirement scores. The findings show that

in none of the dimensions of the scale, namely, Task Fulfilment, Career Development, Learning, and Working Time, significant difference has been noted between the said two groups of participants. Hence, Hypothesis 17, which states that “IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of perceived flexibility requirements”, Hypothesis 17a stating that “IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of task fulfilment dimension of perceived flexibility requirements”, Hypothesis 17b postulating that “IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of career development dimension of perceived flexibility requirements”, Hypothesis 17c stating that “IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of learning dimension of perceived flexibility requirements”, and Hypothesis 17d postulating that “IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of working time dimension of perceived flexibility requirements” are accepted following the present findings.

Table 8 further reveals that employees working remotely reported slightly lower perceived flexibility requirements across all dimensions—Task Fulfilment, Career Development, Learning, and Working Time—compared to those working in hybrid mode. Although the differences are minimal, the trend suggests that hybrid employees may place slightly more value on flexibility across various aspects of their roles. In each of the four dimensions—Task Fulfilment, Career Development, Learning, and Working Time—both groups scored above the midpoint, indicating a consistently high perceived need for flexibility across these domains. The total scores for both groups also exceeded the midpoint, reflecting an overall high level of perceived flexibility requirement regardless of work arrangement.

Fig 8: Diagram representing Perceived Flexibility Requirement scores of IT Employees under Hybrid and Remote Modes

Table 9: Perceived Flexibility Requirement Scores of IT Employees working under On-site and Remote Modes and their Comparisons

Perceived Flexibility Requirement dimensions	On-site (N=50)		Remote (N=50)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
Task Fulfillment	4.0880	0.87520	3.9360	1.14103	0.747*
Career Development	4.5300	1.10384	4.1400	1.32880	1.596*
Learning	4.0500	1.05100	3.8900	1.29477	0.678*
Working Time	3.9300	1.07029	3.9500	1.10426	0.092*
Total	4.1015	0.68458	3.9646	0.87225	0.873*

High score indicates high level of perceived flexibility requirements

*Difference not significant

Table 9 displays the comparison between the two groups of IT employees working under On-site and Remote modes with regard to their scores in the Perceived Flexibility Requirement Scale. The results indicate that the two groups of respondents have not differed significantly in any of the

dimensions of the scale, namely, Task Fulfilment, Career Development, Learning, Working Time, and also in respect of the overall flexibility requirement score. Hence, Hypothesis 12, that is, “IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of perceived flexibility requirements” is accepted. Furthermore, the dimension-specific hypotheses, that is, Hypothesis 12a - “IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of task fulfilment dimension of perceived flexibility requirements”, Hypothesis 12b - “IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of career development dimension of perceived flexibility requirements”, Hypothesis 12c - “IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of learning dimension of perceived flexibility requirements”, and Hypothesis 12d - “IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of working time dimension of perceived flexibility requirements” are also accepted.

Table 9 further indicates that on-site employees reported slightly higher perceived flexibility requirements than their remote counterparts across all dimensions of the scale, except for Working Time, where remote workers scored marginally higher. This suggests that employees working on-site may feel a somewhat greater organizational expectation to remain flexible, particularly in areas such as task fulfilment, career development, and learning. In each of the four dimensions—Task Fulfilment, Career Development, Learning, and Working Time—both groups scored above the midpoint, indicating a high perceived need for flexibility across these areas. The total scores for both groups also exceeded the midpoint, reflecting an overall high level of perceived flexibility requirement, with only minor differences observed based on work arrangement.

Fig 9: Diagram representing Perceived Flexibility Requirement Sores of IT Employees under On-site and Remote Modes

Table 10: Work Autonomy Scores of Male and Female IT Employees and their Comparisons

Work Autonomy dimensions	Male (N=79)		Female (N=75)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
Work Method Autonomy	4.6751	1.52002	4.8178	1.33704	0.617*
Work Scheduling Autonomy	4.3755	1.37785	4.5467	1.36630	0.774*
Work Criteria Autonomy	4.1224	1.29119	4.3022	1.29931	0.861*
Total	4.3910	1.19178	4.5556	1.19125	0.857*

High score indicates high level of perceived autonomy

*Difference not significant

Table 10 presents the comparison between male and female IT employees in respect of their scores in the Work Autonomy Scale, and its dimensions, namely, Work Method Autonomy, Work Scheduling Autonomy, and Work Criteria Autonomy. The results indicate that the said two groups of IT workers have not differed significantly concerning work autonomy or its dimensions. Therefore, Hypothesis 3, stating that, “Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in

respect of work autonomy” is accepted. Moreover, Hypothesis 3a, that is, “Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of work method autonomy dimension”, Hypothesis 3b, that is, “Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of work scheduling autonomy dimension”, and Hypothesis 3c, that is, “Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of work criteria autonomy dimension” are also accepted in view of the present findings.

Table 10 further reveals that female employees reported slightly higher average scores than their male counterparts across all dimensions of work autonomy—Work Method Autonomy, Work Scheduling Autonomy, and Work Criteria Autonomy. This suggests that female IT professionals may perceive marginally greater control over how they perform tasks, manage their schedules, and evaluate their work outcomes. In all three dimensions, as well as the total autonomy score, both groups scored above the midpoint, indicating a generally high level of perceived autonomy across the sample. These findings reflect that male and female IT employees alike experience considerable flexibility and discretion in their work, with only minimal sex-based variation in their autonomy perceptions.

Fig 10: Diagram representing Work Autonomy Scores of Male and Female IT Employees

Table 11: Work Autonomy Scores of IT Employees working under Hybrid and On-site Modes and their Comparisons

Work Autonomy dimensions	Hybrid (N=54)		On-site (N=50)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
Work Method Autonomy	4.5432	1.47416	4.7133	1.47390	0.588*
Work Scheduling Autonomy	4.3210	1.39626	4.2533	1.32576	0.253*
Work Criteria Autonomy	4.0926	1.35736	4.0133	1.28123	0.306*
Total	4.3189	1.18458	4.3267	1.15326	0.034*

High score indicates high level of perceived autonomy

*Difference not significant

Table 11 displays the comparison between IT employees working under hybrid and onsite modes with respect to their scores in the Work Autonomy Scale, including three dimensions, namely, work method autonomy, work scheduling autonomy, and work criteria autonomy. The findings indicate no statistically significant differences between the two groups across all dimensions assessed as well as in the total scale. The findings lead towards acceptance of Hypothesis 8, that is, “IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of work autonomy”, Hypothesis 8a, stating that “IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of work method autonomy”, Hypothesis 8b, stating that “IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of work scheduling autonomy”, and Hypothesis 8c, postulating that “IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of work criteria autonomy”.

According to Table 11, employees working under a hybrid arrangement reported slightly higher levels of autonomy in scheduling their tasks and setting evaluation criteria, while their on-site counterparts exhibited marginally greater autonomy in determining work methods and overall work autonomy. In all three dimensions—Work Method Autonomy, Work Scheduling Autonomy, and Work Criteria Autonomy—as well as in the total score, both groups scored above the midpoint,

indicating a generally high level of perceived autonomy irrespective of work arrangement. These findings suggest that IT employees, regardless of whether they work on-site or in a hybrid mode, experience substantial discretion and control in their work roles, with only minor variations in specific autonomy domains.

Fig 11: Diagram representing Work Autonomy Scores of IT employees under Hybrid and On-site Modes

Table 12: Work Autonomy Scores of IT Employees working under Hybrid and Remote Modes and their Comparisons

Work Autonomy dimensions	Hybrid (N=54)		Remote (N=50)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
Work Method Autonomy	4.5432	1.47416	4.9933	1.32735	1.632*
Work Scheduling Autonomy	4.3210	1.39626	4.8133	1.34377	1.829*
Work Criteria Autonomy	4.0926	1.35736	4.5333	1.19712	1.750*
Total	4.3189	1.18458	4.7800	1.19723	1.973*

High score indicates high level of perceived autonomy

*Difference not significant

Table 12 depicts the comparison between IT employees working under Hybrid and Remote modes in respect of work autonomy and its dimensions. The results indicate that differences between the said two groups of IT workers in all the dimensions, namely, work method, work scheduling and, work criteria and the total scale are not significant. Accordingly, Hypothesis 18, stating that “IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work autonomy”, Hypothesis 18a, that is, “IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work method autonomy”, Hypothesis 18b, that is, “IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work scheduling autonomy”, and Hypothesis 18c, that is, “IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work criteria autonomy” are accepted in view of the obtained findings.

Table 12 further indicates that employees working under remote arrangements reported higher mean scores across all dimensions of work autonomy—Work Method Autonomy, Work Scheduling Autonomy, and Work Criteria Autonomy—compared to those in hybrid mode. This pattern suggests that remote workers may experience greater freedom in choosing how to perform tasks, organize their schedules, and define performance standards. In all three dimensions, as well as the total score, both groups scored above the midpoint, reflecting a high overall level of perceived autonomy. Although remote employees consistently scored higher, the differences were not statistically significant, indicating that the mode of work—whether hybrid or remote—does not meaningfully impact IT employees’ perceptions of work autonomy.

Fig 12: Diagram representing Work Autonomy scores of Hybrid and Remote IT employees**Table 13: Work Autonomy Scores of IT Employees Working under On-site and Remote Modes and their Comparisons**

Work Autonomy dimensions	On-site (N=50)		Remote (N=50)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
Work Method Autonomy	4.7133	1.47390	4.9933	1.32735	0.998*
Work Scheduling Autonomy	4.2533	1.32576	4.8133	1.34377	2.098**
Work Criteria Autonomy	4.0133	1.28123	4.5333	1.19712	2.097**
Total	4.3267	1.15326	4.7800	1.19723	1.928*

High score indicates high level of perceived autonomy

*Difference not significant; ** $p < 0.05$

The comparison between the IT employees working under onsite and remote modes regarding their scores on the Work Autonomy Scale and its dimensions, namely, work method autonomy, work scheduling autonomy, work criteria autonomy has been presented in Table 13. The results indicate statistically significant differences between the two groups in respect of two domains, namely, work scheduling autonomy and work criteria autonomy. Hence, Hypothesis 13b, which states that “IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work

scheduling autonomy”, and Hypothesis 13c, that is, “IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work criteria autonomy” are rejected. Moreover, no significant differences between the said two groups of IT workers have been noted regarding the work method autonomy dimension, and the total Work Autonomy Scale. Therefore, Hypothesis 13a, that is, “IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work method autonomy”, and Hypothesis 13, stating that “IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of work autonomy” are accepted, based on the findings.

Table 13 shows that remote employees reported higher levels of perceived autonomy than their on-site counterparts across all dimensions—Work Method Autonomy, Work Scheduling Autonomy, and Work Criteria Autonomy. The differences were particularly pronounced in Work Scheduling and Work Criteria Autonomy, where the remote group’s scores were significantly higher, suggesting that employees working from home may feel more in control of their schedules and the standards by which their performance is judged. In contrast, the difference in Work Method Autonomy was not statistically significant. Notably, both groups scored above the midpoint across all dimensions and in the total autonomy score, indicating a generally high level of perceived autonomy among IT employees regardless of work mode. These results highlight a stronger perception of independence and self-direction in remote work settings, especially in areas involving time management and performance evaluation.

Fig 13: Diagram representing Work Autonomy scores of On-site and Remote IT employees**Table 14: Job Performance Scores of Male and Female IT Employees and their Comparison**

Job Performance dimensions	Male (N=79)		Female (N=75)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
Task Performance	4.1873	0.69233	4.2400	0.60805	0.500*
Contextual Performance	3.9515	0.68154	3.9533	0.68091	0.017*
Total	4.0587	0.63487	4.0836	0.60593	0.249*

Higher score indicates better perceived performance

*Difference not significant

Table 14 presents the comparison between male and female IT employees based on their scores on the Job Performance Scale, and its dimensions, namely, task performance, contextual performance. The results indicate that the said two groups of IT employees have not differed significantly in respect of any of the domains and also the total scale. The findings lead toward acceptance of Hypothesis 4, stating that “Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of job performance”, Hypothesis 4a, that is, “Male and female IT employees do not differ

significantly in respect of task performance”, and Hypothesis 4b, that is, “Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of contextual performance”.

As evident from Table 14, female IT employees reported slightly higher levels of perceived job performance than their male counterparts across both dimensions—Task Performance and Contextual Performance. The total job performance score also reflects a marginal advantage for female employees. However, these differences were not statistically significant, indicating that sex does not have a meaningful influence on perceived job performance. Importantly, both male and female employees scored well above the midpoint across all dimensions and the total scale, suggesting a generally high level of self-perceived job performance within the IT workforce.

Fig 14: Diagram representing Job Performance scores of male and female IT employees

Table 15: Job Performance Scores of IT Employees Working under Hybrid and On-site Modes and their Comparisons

Job Performance dimensions	Hybrid (N=54)		On-site (N=50)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
Task Performance	4.2407	0.67559	4.1640	0.69363	0.571*
Contextual Performance	3.9599	0.68216	3.8733	0.71235	0.633*
Total	4.0875	0.64403	4.0055	0.62592	0.658*

Higher score indicates better perceived performance

*Difference not significant

Table 15 presents the comparison between IT employees working under hybrid and onsite modes regarding their scores on the Job Performance Scale, and its two dimensions. The differences between the said groups of workers are found not to be significant in any of the domains, as also the total score. Accordingly, Hypothesis 9, stating that “IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of job performance”, Hypothesis 9a, which states that “IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of task performance”, and Hypothesis 9b, that is, “IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of contextual performance” are accepted.

Table 15 indicates that employees working in a hybrid mode reported slightly higher mean scores than their on-site counterparts across both dimensions of job performance—Task Performance and Contextual Performance—as well as in the overall score. Although these differences were not statistically significant, the trend suggests that hybrid employees may perceive themselves as somewhat more effective in task execution and in demonstrating cooperative behaviours, effort, and compliance with workplace norms. In all dimensions and the total score, both groups scored well above the midpoint, indicating a generally high level of perceived job performance among IT employees regardless of work mode.

Fig 15: Diagram representing Job Performance scores of Hybrid and On-site IT employees**Table 16: Job Performance Scores of IT Employees Working under Hybrid and Remote Modes and their comparisons**

Job Performance dimensions	Hybrid (N=54)		Remote (N=50)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
Task Performance	4.2407	0.67559	4.2320	0.58743	0.070*
Contextual Performance	3.9599	0.68216	4.0233	0.64594	0.486*
Total	4.0875	0.64403	4.1182	0.59094	0.252*

Higher score indicates better perceived performance

*Difference not significant

The comparison between the IT employees working under hybrid and remote arrangements, based on job performance and its two domains, namely, task performance, contextual performance, is presented in Table 16. It is evident from the table that in none of the domains and also the total scale, the two groups of employees have differed significantly. The findings lead towards acceptance of Hypothesis 19, stating that “IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of job performance”, Hypothesis 19a, which states that “IT employees

working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of task performance”, and Hypothesis 19b, which postulates that “IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of contextual performance”.

Table 16 shows that hybrid and remote employees reported comparable levels of perceived job performance across both task and contextual dimensions. Hybrid workers scored slightly higher in the Task Performance domain, while remote employees reported marginally higher mean scores in Contextual Performance and the overall job performance scale. These minor variations, however, were not statistically significant, indicating that the mode of work—whether hybrid or remote—does not meaningfully influence perceived job performance. Both groups scored well above the midpoint across all dimensions and the total scale, suggesting a generally high level of perceived job performance among IT professionals in both work arrangements.

Fig 16: Diagram representing Job Performance scores of Hybrid and Remote IT employees

Table 17: Job Performance Scores of IT Employees Working under On-site and Remote Modes and their Comparisons

Job Performance dimensions	On-site (N=50)		Remote (N=50)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
Task Performance	4.1640	0.69363	4.2320	0.58743	0.529*
Contextual Performance	3.8733	0.71235	4.0233	0.64594	1.103*
Total	4.0055	0.62592	4.1182	0.59094	0.926*

Higher score indicates better perceived performance

*Difference not significant

Table 17 presents the comparison between IT employees working under onsite and remote modes regarding their scores on the Job Performance Scale, and its domains. The results indicate that the two groups of respondents have not differed significantly not only in respect of the domains but also in the total scale. Accordingly, Hypothesis 14, stating that “IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of job performance”, Hypothesis 14a, which states that “IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of task performance”, and Hypothesis 14b, that is, “IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of contextual performance” are accepted.

Table 17 indicates that IT employees working remotely reported slightly higher average scores than their on-site counterparts across both Task Performance and Contextual Performance dimensions, as well as in the overall job performance score. This suggests that remote employees may perceive themselves as performing core job duties and supplementary functions—such as cooperating with colleagues, showing initiative, and adhering to workplace norms—marginally better than those working on-site. However, these differences were not statistically significant. Both groups scored well above the midpoint across all dimensions and the total scale, reflecting a generally high level of perceived job performance, regardless of work mode.

Fig 17: Diagram representing Job Performance scores of On-site and Remote IT employees**Table 18: Perceived Organizational Support Scores of Male and Female IT Employees and their Comparison**

Perceived Organizational Support	Male (N=79)		Female (N=75)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
	4.6013	0.95493	4.7250	0.94373	

High score indicates high level of perceived organizational support

*Difference not significant

Table 18 presents the comparison between male and female IT employees regarding their scores on the Perceived Organizational Support Scale. The results indicate that there is no statistically significant difference between the two groups of employees, in respect of sex. Hence, Hypothesis 5, stating that “Male and female IT employees do not differ significantly in respect of perceived organizational support” is accepted.

Table 18 further shows that female IT employees reported slightly higher average scores than their male counterparts on the Perceived Organizational Support Scale, suggesting that women may feel marginally more valued and supported by their organizations. This includes perceptions that management recognizes their contributions and cares about their well-being. Despite this slight difference, the scores for both groups were well above the midpoint, indicating a generally high level of perceived organizational support among male and female IT employees alike. The minimal variation between the groups suggests that sex does not meaningfully influence perceptions of support from the organization.

Fig 18: Diagram representing Perceived Organizational Support scores of male and female IT employees

Table 19: Perceived Organizational Support Scores of IT Employees Working under Hybrid and On-site Modes and their Comparison

Perceived Organizational Support	Hybrid (N=54)		On-site (N=50)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
	4.6898	0.96389	4.3600	1.01633	1.698*

High score indicates high level of perceived organizational support

*Difference not significant

The comparison between the IT employees working under hybrid and onsite modes regarding their scores on the Perceived Organizational Support Scale has been depicted in Table 19. It is evident from the table that the difference between the two groups of IT workers has not been statistically significant. Therefore, Hypothesis 10, stating that “IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes do not differ significantly in respect of perceived organizational support” is accepted.

Table 19 reveals that employees working under a hybrid arrangement reported slightly higher levels of perceived organizational support compared to their on-site counterparts, based on the average scores. This suggests that hybrid employees may feel marginally more valued and cared for by their organizations. However, the difference was not statistically significant. Both groups scored above the midpoint, indicating a generally high level of perceived organizational support across work arrangements. These findings suggest that the mode of work—whether hybrid or on-site—does not substantially influence IT employees’ perceptions of how much support they receive from their organizations.

Fig 19: Diagram representing Perceived Organizational Support scores of Hybrid and On-site IT employees

Table 20: Perceived Organizational Support Scores of IT Employees Working under Hybrid and Remote Modes and their Comparison

Perceived Organizational Support	Hybrid (N=54)		Remote (N=50)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
	4.6898	0.96389	4.9325	0.77600	1.407*

High score indicates high level of perceived organizational support

*Difference not significant

Table 20 shows the comparison between the IT employees working under hybrid and remote work arrangements, based on their scores on the Perceived Organizational Support scale. The results indicate no statistically significant difference between the two groups in their overall perceived organizational support. Accordingly, Hypothesis 20, stating that “IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of perceived organizational support” is accepted.

Table 20 indicates that employees working remotely reported slightly higher levels of perceived organizational support compared to those in hybrid arrangements, suggesting that remote workers may feel somewhat more recognized and cared for by their organizations. Despite this difference, the results were not statistically significant. Both groups scored above the midpoint, reflecting a generally high level of perceived organizational support across both work arrangements. These findings imply that the mode of work—whether hybrid or remote—does not meaningfully influence IT employees’ perceptions of support from their organizations.

Fig 20: Diagram representing Perceived Organizational Support scores of Hybrid and Remote IT employees

Table 21: Perceived Organizational Support Scores of IT Employees Working under On-site and Remote Modes and their Comparison

Perceived Organizational Support	On-site (N=50)		Remote (N=50)		t-value
	Mean	S. D.	Mean	S. D.	
	4.3600	1.01633	4.9325	.77600	3.166**

High score indicates high level of perceived organizational support

*Difference not significant; ** $p < 0.05$

Table 21 presents the comparison between the IT employees placed under onsite and remote modes of work regarding their scores on the Perceived Organizational Support Scale. The results indicate that the said two groups of IT workers have differed significantly regarding perceived organizational support. The finding leads towards rejection of Hypothesis 15, which postulates that “IT employees working under on-site and remote modes do not differ significantly in respect of perceived organizational support”.

Table 21 highlights that IT employees working remotely reported significantly higher levels of perceived organizational support compared to their on-site counterparts. This suggests that remote workers are more likely to feel that their organizations value their contributions and care about their well-being. The difference in mean scores was statistically significant, indicating that work mode may have a meaningful impact on how supported employees feel. Notably, both groups scored above the midpoint, reflecting an overall high level of perceived organizational support. However, the considerably higher scores among remote employees point to a stronger sense of recognition and support in remote work environments.

Fig 21: Diagram representing Perceived Organizational Support scores of On-site and Remote IT employees

4.2) Discussion

This section discusses the findings of the present study in relation to the hypotheses and existing literature. Each psychological variable is examined across sex and work arrangement. The results are interpreted in view of the recent changes in the Indian IT sector, with possible reasons offered for both significant and non-significant outcomes.

Work-Family Conflict

The findings presented in Tables 2 through 5 indicate that there are no statistically significant differences in work-family conflict across sex and work arrangement among early-career IT professionals in India. The findings presented in Table 2, that is, lack of significant difference between male and female IT employees in both work to family and family to work conflicts are not in support of the observations of Deshwal, Gupta, and Kararha (2021), and Shockley et al. (2017). The researchers found women reporting significantly higher levels of work-family conflict than men in different industries, including IT. The present sample of male and female IT employees, however, have been found to experience comparable levels of work-to-family conflict and family-to-work conflict. This aligns with the recent shifts in the IT sector where the traditional expectations regarding household and professional role playing are undergoing changes due to increased female workforce participation and prevalence of egalitarian gender roles nowadays.

Table 2 further shows a slightly higher average score of the female respondents than their male counterparts in respect of overall work-family conflict, which is in conformity with the research findings of Thriveni Kumari (2022), Deshwal, Gupta, and Kararha (2021), and Shockley et al. (2017), all of whom found women to experience higher levels of work-family conflict than men, particularly due to domestic responsibilities interfering with work. However, the current study reveals that males have reported slightly more work-to-family conflict than their female colleagues. Similar trend had been noted by Hungund, Gujanal, and Suresh (2024),

in a study of 179 IT professionals in Bengaluru. The female employees, on the other hand, have experienced marginally higher family-to-work conflict. Though these differences are not statistically significant, they suggest the persistence of role-specific stressors. This echoes Thriveni Kumari's (2022) observations that while women may encounter family obligations intruding into work, men may be more burdened by external work stressors like deadlines, long commutes, and performance pressures.

The non-significant sex difference found here may reflect a shifting trend in urban Indian IT settings, where improved access to domestic help, increasing number of dual-income households, and greater awareness of sex roles are helping people to balance work and family demands, irrespective of sex. Moreover, the fact that majority of the present sample have reported of being single and child-free may explain equitable levels of work-family conflict across sex.

The comparison across work arrangements reveals no significant differences in work-family conflict among the selected group of IT employees (Tables 3 through 5). Further analysis of average scores obtained by the three groups of employees indicates that the employees working under the traditional on-site mode have the highest level of work-family conflict. The finding is in conformity with the research observation of Christy et al. (2021), who reported that office work increased work-family conflict due to inflexible schedules. Other researchers, however, reported an opposite trend. For instance, Vattapparambath (2023) observed that traditional work-from-office (WFO) setups offered clearer separation between work and personal life, than the other modes of work, thereby may reduce workers' work-family conflict. The finding matches with that of Christy et al. (2021), according to whom, work-from-home due to greater flexibility and reduced commuting supported better work-life balance. The present sample of IT employees working from home (remote) has been found to experience the lowest amount of work-family conflict. The employees working under the

hybrid mode have been found to express intermediate levels of work-family conflict. Santos et al. (2024) too considered hybrid arrangements as a potentially optimal structure. It is noteworthy that in the work-to-family domain, the remote employees have average level of conflict, whereas those under traditional and hybrid modes have expressed slightly above average levels. Sharma and Sharma (2024) and Vattapparambath (2023) observed that hybrid workers often experienced increased role blurring and emotional strain, especially when working from home without dedicated workspaces. However, the present sample's comparable scores suggest that the participants, most of whom are in their early career stages and without caregiving responsibilities may not face the same level of competing demands between home and work domains.

Greenhaus and Beutell (1985) proposed that the domain which imposes more time and energy demands is more likely to create conflict for the other. Employees working in the traditional on-site mode may bring work-related stress and deadlines into their home sphere, while those working from home may find domestic responsibilities encroaching on professional tasks, especially in the absence of clear boundaries.

The minimal difference in work-family conflict scores across all groups, based on gender and work arrangement suggests that early-career IT professionals, despite their demanding roles, may be adapting well to different work formats. This could be attributed to better digital infrastructure, autonomy, or supportive team dynamics commonly found in India's IT sector post-pandemic. It is also possible that organizational expectations for boundary-setting and time management have improved following the widespread adoption of hybrid and remote models.

In essence, while minor trends reflecting sex-role spillovers and domain interference are observed, the lack of statistically significant differences points toward an emerging parity in how young IT employees experience work-family conflict, regardless of gender or work

mode. This finding supports the idea that contextual factors, such as age, family status, and organizational support structures may be moderating the traditionally observed patterns of conflict in this domain.

Perceived Flexibility Requirements

The findings presented in Table 6 indicate that no statistically significant difference exists between male and female IT employees, in respect of perceived flexibility requirements and its domains, namely, task fulfilment, career development, learning, and working time. The finding is contradicted by those of earlier researchers (Shockley and Shen, 2020; De Menezes and Kelliher, 2020; Kossek et al., 2019; and Chung and van der Horst, 2018), who reported sex differences in flexibility requirements.

Further analysis of findings presented in Table 6 shows that regarding all the domains as well as overall perceived flexibility requirements, the male respondents have scored higher on average than their female counterparts, which is in contrary to earlier research findings of Shockley and Shen (2020), De Menezes and Kelliher (2020), Kossek et al. (2019), Butts, Casper and Yang (2019), and Chung and van der Horst (2018), according to whom female employees not only reported significantly higher flexibility requirements, but also required more flexibility to balance their professional and family roles, as compared to their male counterparts. It is noteworthy that in all domains as well as in respect of total scale, the present sample of respondents have expressed average flexibility requirements, irrespective of gender.

In the present case, although the differences between male and female respondents have been non-significant, they may reflect subtle variations in how male and female employees interpret organizational expectations for adaptability. It is noteworthy that majority of the present sample are unmarried, childless participants who need not to juggle overlapping domestic responsibilities alongside work tasks, leading to more homogenous perceptions of flexibility requirements. Interestingly, while previous literature like that of Chung and van der

Horst (2018) and De Menezes and Kelliher (2020) highlighted that women often need flexibility to balance work and family, the current results suggest that in early-career Indian IT settings, flexibility may be viewed more as a professional expectation than a personal accommodation, which is equally applicable for employees irrespective of their gender. This aligns with Butts et al. (2019), who observed that flexibility in IT and knowledge sectors has shifted from being a benefit to an implicit job demand, driven by constant connectivity and project-based work cycles. Moreover, Kossek et al. (2019) suggested that traditional sex roles shaped flexibility requirements, influencing women's experiences more heavily in balancing work and family. The prevalence of egalitarian sex-roles nowadays, might have played a role in balancing perception of flexibility requirements in both men and women.

The comparison of perceived flexibility requirements of the present sample of IT respondents in terms of mode of work have not revealed any statistically significant difference in any of the dimensions of the scale (Tables 7, 8, and 9). The findings do not corroborate with those of Wontorczyk and Roznowski (2022), and Gajendran, Harrison, and Delaney-Klinger (2021), who suggested that work arrangements substantially influenced how flexibility was interpreted, as either empowering or burdensome.

The lack of significant differences suggests that IT employees, regardless of work mode, may be internalizing flexibility as a professional norm, especially in a sector characterized by fast-paced delivery cycles, client time-zone dependencies, and a results-driven culture. The non-significant but moderate scores secured by respondents belonging to all three groups, based on work arrangement underscore the pervasiveness of flexibility expectations in modern IT roles where adaptability instead of stability is seen as the marker of a committed and high-performing employee.

Tables 7 through 9 further reveal that those working under remote arrangement have the lowest levels of perceived flexibility requirements; whereas the employees placed under

hybrid mode have the highest flexibility requirements in respect of all dimensions, except career development. The on-site workers are in the intermediate positions based on their average scores in the dimensions of perceived flexibility requirement. Moreover, the present sample of IT personnel, irrespective of the work arrangement have expressed comparable levels, more specifically average levels of flexibility requirements concerning the dimensions, namely, task fulfilment, career development, learning, and working time, as well as the total scale. The present findings are in contrary to earlier research observations of Wontorczyk and Roznowski (2022), and Gajendran, Harrison, and Delaney-Klinger (2021). None of the researchers found the remote workers to express the lowest level of flexibility requirements. Wontorczyk and Roznowski (2022) observed the remote workers reported the highest perceived flexibility requirements, due to lack of structure and expectations of constant availability. The on-site workers, on the other hand, displayed the lowest perceived flexibility requirements, due to the structured and predictable nature of their work environment. Gajendran, Harrison, and Delaney-Klinger (2021) found that the workers on hybrid mode experienced lower perceived flexibility strain than fully remote or on-site employees. The highest perceived flexibility requirements of the present sample of hybrid workers may be attributed to the fact that the hybrid employees often juggle changing schedules and locations, which potentially increases their perceived need to remain adaptable. Moreover, the lowest perceived flexibility needs of the remote workers might reflect their greater control over time and fewer visible performance pressures.

It is worth noting that the perceived flexibility requirement variable is relatively underexplored in the Indian IT context. While earlier studies (e.g., Thomas and Höge, 2013) conceptualize flexibility as a supportive resource, the current study supports a growing narrative that flexibility may function as an implicit demand creating pressure on employees to be available and responsive beyond conventional work hours.

In essence, the present findings highlight that the selected sample of early-career IT professionals across sex and work modes have reported comparable levels of perceived flexibility requirement. This may indicate a cultural shift in the Indian IT sector where flexibility is not a discretionary benefit but an ingrained expectation, affecting all employees similarly, irrespective of their demographic or work arrangement background. However, there is a need for further qualitative exploration to understand how these expectations are internalized and managed.

Work Autonomy

The findings derived from Table 10 suggest that no statistically significant difference exists between male and female IT employees in the experience of work autonomy, as well as its dimensions, namely, work method, work scheduling, and work criteria. Moreover, the female employees have reported slightly higher average scores across all three dimensions of autonomy as well as the total score, in comparison to the males. While these differences were not statistically significant, the pattern is notable in contrast to the broader literature, where women are often reported to have lower experienced autonomy despite formal access to flexible arrangements. For instance, Chung and van der Horst (2018) and Craig and Brown (2017) observed that caregiving roles and organizational culture often limited women's actual control over their work, even when autonomy was formally provided.

The present sample consists largely of young, unmarried, and child-free professionals, which could mitigate traditional caregiving-role related restrictions. The slightly higher perceived autonomy among female respondents may reflect an evolving work culture in the Indian IT sector that is increasingly egalitarian, or possibly a greater sense of self-regulation and time management among women at the early stages of their careers. This observation is consistent with the argument of Kossek and Lautsch (2018), who noted that perceptions of autonomy are often shaped more by managerial trust and role expectations than by sex alone.

Tables 11, 12, and 13 show that the comparison of employees' work autonomy across different work arrangements, that is, hybrid, on-site, and remote reveals largely non-significant differences, except for two dimensions, namely, work scheduling and work criteria, where remote employees have differed significantly from their on-site counterparts.

When examining differences in work autonomy in respect of work arrangement, the findings suggest that remote workers have consistently displayed higher scores across all dimensions of work autonomy compared to hybrid and on-site workers. The significant differences between remote and on-site employees concerning work scheduling autonomy and work criteria autonomy indicate that employees working from home perceive greater freedom in determining their schedules and performance standards. These findings are in line with prior studies, including those of Bloom et al. (2015) and Zhou et al. (2020), who confirmed that remote employees benefited from enhanced control over task execution and time management, although such benefits were sometimes moderated by factors, such as digital proficiency and home infrastructure.

Interestingly, the hybrid group's autonomy scores were closer to those of on-site employees than to the remote group. This suggests that although hybrid employees do benefit from partial flexibility, their autonomy may still be constrained by in-office requirements, team schedules, or managerial oversight. These results echo the findings of Rai and Ghosh (2022), who reported that hybrid workers in India experience moderate levels of autonomy, balancing between structured routines and flexible days.

Furthermore, the significant differences observed between remote and on-site workers in the domains of work scheduling and performance criteria affirm that physical distance from the workplace fosters greater perception of control. This may be attributed to reduced direct supervision and greater reliance on output-based performance evaluation systems in remote setups, as discussed by Ono (2022). At the same time, the fact that remote and on-site workers

did not differ significantly regarding work method autonomy indicates that regardless of work location, procedures and tools may be standardized across teams, especially in IT roles that require uniform codebases or shared platforms.

Overall, the findings suggest that remote work enables higher perceived autonomy, particularly in time management and evaluation, while hybrid and on-site roles are more bounded by structured routines. The absence of sex differences in work autonomy may reflect the early-career status of the sample and a relatively equitable distribution of work responsibilities in today's IT organizations. However, the significance of autonomy in shaping other outcomes like job performance and well-being warrants deeper investigation in future. In essence, work autonomy is influenced more by work arrangement than by sex, with remote employees experiencing the highest degree of perceived control, particularly in scheduling and evaluation. These findings highlight the importance of promoting autonomy-supportive practices across all work formats to foster employee engagement and productivity in India's evolving IT landscape.

Job Performance

As per Table 14, male and female IT employees have not differed significantly in respect of job performance and its dimensions, namely, task performance and contextual performance, with women scoring slightly higher than their male counterparts in both task and contextual domains. This is in contradiction with the findings of Deshwal, Gupta, and Kararha (2021), that is, male participants were found to score higher in job performance than females. Although the differences between the present samples of male and female workers are not statistically significant, they do reflect a pattern observed in earlier literature where women often compensate for role-related expectations through higher engagement and diligence, especially in collaborative or supportive work contexts. For instance, Vega, Anderson, and Kaplan (2015) observed that while women in remote and on-site modes displayed comparable

technical competencies to men, their performance was more susceptible to disruptions from home-related duties. However, in the present sample, where a vast majority of participants were unmarried and without children, such confounding factors may have been minimized.

The near-equal levels of perception of job performance reported by male and female respondents aligns with research observations of Shockley et al. (2017), that is, sex-based differences in job performance were minimal after accounting for work-family conflict, as elevated conflict among women correlated negatively with both task and contextual performances among them. Moreover, it may also reflect the standardized performance evaluation mechanisms used in IT industries, often guided by output metrics, key performance indicators (KPIs), and agile methodologies that apply uniformly across sex lines.

When comparing groups of employees based on work arrangement, no significant differences were noted in the domains as well as the total scale (Tables 15, 16, and 17). Moreover, job performance was perceived to be slightly higher in hybrid and remote groups than in on-site groups. Hybrid workers scored marginally better in task performance, while remote workers had the highest scores in contextual performance and overall job performance. These results mirror those reported by Choudhury, Foroughi, and Larson (2021), who found that hybrid employees excelled in both independent and collaborative tasks; and remote workers outperformed others in focused, individual work. Similarly, Allen et al. (2015), in their meta-analysis, highlighted that remote work can enhance job performance by minimizing distractions, and offering control over the work environment.

The fact that on-site employees reported the lowest job performance scores, even if not significantly so, may suggest that rigid office routines, commuting stress, and environmental distractions could be limiting their perceived productivity. This observation aligns with the findings of Kumar and Velmurugan (2022), who reported that hybrid and remote employees

often enjoy better job satisfaction and efficiency due to flexible scheduling and reduced physical barriers.

Interestingly, the differences in performance scores across modes were statistically not significant, which may indicate that employee performance in IT is less contingent on work location, and more influenced by organizational support systems, task clarity, and access to digital tools. In an industry where deliverables are often managed through collaborative platforms, time-bound sprints, and digital communication tools, the place of work may no longer be a strong determinant of how performance is perceived.

Furthermore, the equitable distribution of performance ratings across sex and mode highlights that early-career professionals, often in execution roles may not experience as much variability in responsibilities or output expectations as senior-level employees might. This uniformity also reinforces the idea that remote and hybrid models, when properly structured, do not hinder performance and may, in fact, offer marginal advantages in certain task domains.

In essence, the present findings support the conclusion that job performance among early-career IT employees remains consistent across sex and work arrangements, with hybrid and remote roles showing slight but non-significant advantages. These insights reinforce the growing body of research suggesting that performance outcomes in digitally-enabled industries depend more on task design, autonomy, and support systems than on physical presence at the workplace.

Perceived Organizational Support (POS)

Table 18 reflects that the difference between male and female IT employees has not been significant in respect of perceived organizational support, with the female employees perceiving slightly greater level of support from the organization than their male colleagues. The finding contradicts that of Al-Taie and Khattak (2024) who indicated a significant sex-based disparity in perceived organizational support. Moreover, according to earlier researchers

(Al-Taie and Khattak, 2024; and Agarwal, 2016), male employees perceived higher levels of support from their organizations than females. This is particularly interesting given that prior research including Agarwal (2016) and Kurtessis et al. (2017) has often highlighted that women tend to perceive less support, especially in male-dominated, performance-oriented sectors like IT. In the current sample, the reverse trend, though minimal, may suggest inclusive HR practices in the Indian IT sector. Additionally, given that the female participants in this study were predominantly early-career, unmarried, and without caregiving responsibilities, their experiences of workplace support may have been less constrained by domestic expectations or structural biases typically encountered at higher career levels.

The findings also align with Poczowski and Urbaniak (2023), who argued that men and women value different aspects of organizational support—while men may emphasize instrumental benefits, such as promotions or pay, women often value relational support like feedback, interpersonal communication, and inclusive culture. The slightly higher average score among female respondents could reflect their greater appreciation for emotional and communicative dimensions of organizational support, which may have become more visible in post-pandemic hybrid or remote work models.

The comparison based on work arrangement indicates a significant difference between on-site and remote employees' perception of organizational support (Table 21), and non-significant differences between hybrid and on-site (Table 19) and hybrid and remote workers (Table 20). When comparing employees placed under different work arrangements, perceived organizational support has been found to be slightly higher in hybrid than in on-site settings, and the highest in case of remote mode. This result contradicts several prior studies, such as those conducted by Zito et al. (2021) and Jung et al. (2021), who documented lower perceived organizational support among remote workers, often attributing it to limited face-to-face contact and reduced informal engagement with peers and supervisors. However, the current

findings may be reflective of a cultural and technological shift in Indian IT firms post-COVID-19. Many organizations have adapted well to digital modes of communication, implemented regular check-ins, virtual recognitions, and transparent workflows, all of which can enhance the feeling of support, even from a distance.

Furthermore, remote employees may interpret the very act of being granted independence of location as a sign of organizational trust and value, thereby inflating their POS perceptions. This is consistent with the observations of Yuhyung and Youngkeun (2021), that is, remote workers in structured, communication-rich environments reported comparable or even higher support levels than their on-site peers, particularly when remote work was framed as a strategic option rather than a necessity.

The significantly lower POS scores among on-site workers may suggest a growing disparity in employee expectations. Those still working on-site may feel disconnected from the flexible and autonomy-driven workplace narratives that dominate contemporary discourse, possibly perceiving themselves as overlooked or underappreciated. This highlights a potential psychological cost of physical presence in a system increasingly designed for digital operations and flexibility.

Taken together, these findings suggest that perceived organizational support is shaped more strongly by work arrangement than by sex. Remote workers, in particular, appear to benefit from a psychological sense of value and trust; while on-site employees may require greater engagement and recognition efforts to offset potential feelings of being left out of modern organizational flexibility paradigms.

In essence, the present study finds that while sex differences in POS are minimal, remote work arrangements significantly enhance perceived support among early-career IT professionals in India. Organizations aiming to maintain morale and retention across all formats

must ensure that recognition, inclusion, and support systems are equitably distributed, regardless of employees' physical location.

In summary, while the current study revealed largely non-significant differences in respect of the selected psychological variables across sex and work modes, the findings highlight important shifts in work culture, professional expectations, and demographic trends within the Indian IT sector. These patterns suggest a gradual blurring of traditional disparities, particularly among early-career professionals. Future research should explore these dynamics longitudinally and across organizational levels to better understand how evolving work structures shape psychological outcomes.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY AND

CONCLUSION

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

5.1) Summary:

The chief objective of the present study was to compare a sample of IT employees across India based on five psychological constructs, namely, work-family conflict, perceived flexibility, work autonomy, job performance, and perceived organizational support, in respect of sex and work arrangements (on-site, hybrid, and remote). The study further aimed to assess whether significant differences existed across the said constructs and their dimensions in respect of gender and work arrangements.

To fulfil the objectives of the study, a total of 64 hypotheses were formulated, the details of which are presented under Methodology, Chapter-3.

A total number of 154 Information Technology employees, comprising 79 males and 75 females, were selected as the sample using purposive sampling technique based on certain predetermined criteria. Among the selected respondents, 50 were working under on-site arrangements, 54 under hybrid, and 50 under remote work settings. The details regarding selection of sample are mentioned under Methodology, Chapter-3.

During the investigation, five standardized psychological scales, namely, Work-Family Conflict Scale (Netemeyer, Boles, and McMurrian, 1996), Perceived Flexibility Requirements Scale (Höge and Hornung, 2015), Work Autonomy Scale (Breugh, 1985), Job Performance Scale (Çalışkan and Köroğlu, 2022), and the 8-item version of Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (Eisenberger et al., 1986), along with a General Information Schedule developed by the present investigator, were employed to collect data from the respondents. The description of the tools has been presented under Methodology, Chapter-3.

Data were collected exclusively through online mode, using a structured Google Form. After completion of data collection, responses were scored using standard scoring keys. Suitable descriptive statistics and independent samples t test were applied to test the stated

hypotheses. The detailed procedure of data collection, scoring, and statistical analysis has been outlined under Methodology, Chapter-3.

Finally, the obtained findings have been presented under Results and Discussion in Chapter-4.

5.2) Concluding Remarks:

The present study was undertaken with the assumption that the current sample of Indian IT employees would not differ significantly in respect of work-family conflict, perceived flexibility requirement, work autonomy, job performance, and perceived organizational support on the basis of sex (male and female) and work arrangement (on-site, hybrid, and remote).

The findings of the present study are summarized below:

- Male and female IT employees have not differed significantly in respect of work-family conflict and its dimensions, namely, work-to-family conflict and family-to-work conflict.
- No significant difference has been found between the IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes in respect of work-family conflict and its dimensions.
- No significant difference has been found between the IT employees working under on-site and remote modes in respect of work-family conflict and its dimensions.
- No significant difference has been found between the IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes in respect of work-family conflict and its dimensions.
- Male and female IT employees have not differed significantly in respect of perceived flexibility requirement and its dimensions, namely, task fulfilment, career development, learning, and working time.
- No significant difference has been found between the IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes in respect of perceived flexibility requirement and its dimensions.

- No significant difference has been found between the IT employees working under on-site and remote modes in respect of perceived flexibility requirement and its dimensions.
- No significant difference has been found between the IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes in respect of perceived flexibility requirement and its dimensions.
- Male and female IT employees have not differed significantly in respect of work autonomy and its dimensions, namely, work method autonomy, work scheduling autonomy, and work criteria autonomy.
- No significant difference has been found between the IT employees under on-site and hybrid modes in respect of work autonomy and its dimensions.
- No significant difference has been found between the IT employees under hybrid and remote modes in respect of work autonomy and its dimensions.
- Statistically significant differences have been found between the IT employees under remote and on-site modes regarding work scheduling autonomy and work criteria autonomy domains, indicating greater perceived control among the remote workers in these two dimensions.
- Male and female IT employees have not differed significantly in respect of job performance and its domains, namely, task performance and contextual performance.
- No significant difference has been found between the IT employees working under on-site and hybrid modes in respect of job performance and its dimensions.
- No significant difference has been found between the IT employees working under on-site and remote modes in respect of job performance and its dimensions.
- No significant difference has been found between the IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes in respect of job performance and its dimensions.

- Male and female IT employees have not differed significantly in respect of perceived organizational support.
- No significant difference has been found between the IT employees working under hybrid and remote modes in respect of perceived organizational support.
- No significant difference has been found between the IT employees working under hybrid and on-site modes in respect of perceived organizational support.
- Significant difference has been found between the IT employees working under remote and on-site modes in respect of perceived organizational support, with remote employees reporting higher levels of support.

In essence, while gender did not significantly affect any of the psychological variables under study, the mode of work arrangement showed specific impacts, particularly in the domains of work autonomy and perceived organizational support. These findings indicate that the scope of working from home (remote mode) may provide employees with a greater sense of autonomy and organizational backing, whereas other psychological outcomes appear relatively stable across sex and work mode.

5.3) Limitations of the Study:

- The data collection phase was restricted by a short timeline and limited outreach. As a result, several potential participants could not be reached or did not respond, which may have affected the diversity and volume of the sample. To ensure timely completion of the study, data were collected entirely through online mode, which may have restricted participation from individuals in areas with limited internet access or low digital literacy.
- A larger and more diverse sample would have enhanced the generalizability of the findings to the broader population of IT employees in India. A wider sample could have

also enabled subgroup comparisons across more granular work roles and levels of experience.

- While demographic data, such as age, marital status, educational qualification, job role, and total work experience were collected, these variables could not be examined as the correlates or predictors of the psychological constructs under study, due to paucity of time. Analysing these dimensions in future research could provide deeper insights into how individual characteristics interact with work arrangements and influence employee performance.
- Although the sample was drawn from several Indian states and union territories, it remained unevenly distributed, with significant clustering in a few states, such as West Bengal, Karnataka, and Maharashtra. Broader and more balanced geographical representation including other states could have enhanced the external validity of the findings, and captured regional variations in work culture and organizational infrastructure.
- The study employed a cross-sectional design, capturing psychological perceptions at a single point in time. However, variables like work autonomy, organizational support, and work-family conflict may vary with changes in job roles, project cycles, or organizational policies. A longitudinal approach might be adopted in future research to assess temporal shifts in these constructs.
- Although the participants represented a range of professional experiences, a noticeable proportion of the respondents were in the early stages of their careers. While this offers valuable insight into the experiences of younger professionals, inclusion of a more balanced distribution across seniority levels and job hierarchies would have provided a more comprehensive perspective.

- As all variables were assessed through self-report measures, there was a possibility of response bias, such as social desirability or inaccurate self-evaluation. While all tools used were standardized, future research might incorporate multi-source feedback (e.g., supervisor or peer ratings) for job performance and organizational support to triangulate findings.

5.4) Applied Value of the Study:

The present study holds significant applied value in the context of the evolving workplace landscape in India's burgeoning Information Technology sector. The study provides a timely psychological lens into how work arrangements, namely on-site, hybrid, and remote, shape employees' lived experiences in terms of work-family conflict, perceived flexibility requirements, work autonomy, job performance, and perceived organizational support. These psychological constructs are not only central to individual well-being and professional functioning, but are also essential drivers of workforce sustainability, productivity, and long-term organizational success.

Over the past few years, the global shift toward hybrid and remote work models has prompted Indian companies to replace traditional work mode by the new arrangements, to a considerable extent. This transition, however, is often implemented without adequate attention to the psychological wellbeing of employees. Findings from the present study suggest that remote work arrangements may offer advantages in terms of perceived autonomy and organizational support - two critical elements that directly affect workers' work motivation, satisfaction, and retention. By empirically demonstrating the differences among various work modes in respect of the concerned psychological constructs, the present study equips human resource professionals, team leaders, and policy architects with data-backed insights to create more employee-centric work environments.

The present research also emphasizes that not all forms of flexibility are beneficial, as supported by Wang, Liu, and Parker (2021), who found that when flexibility is framed as an implicit requirement rather than a voluntary benefit, it becomes a stressor for employees—especially for those balancing work and personal responsibilities. Perceived flexibility requirements, when experienced as an unspoken pressure to be constantly available or adaptable rather than genuine freedom, can blur work-life boundaries, and contribute to burnout or disengagement. Organizations, therefore, must distinguish between empowering flexibility and exploitative flexibility, and design policies that prioritize employee agency, clear expectations, and work-life integration. Such clarity can lead to healthier work climates, particularly in high-pressure industries, such as software development, IT consulting, and data engineering.

Moreover, the study sheds light on the relatively stable experience of psychological variables irrespective of sex, indicating that workplace outcomes are more influenced by structural and cultural dimensions than by biological sex alone. This challenges the stereotypical assumptions around gender roles in the workforce, and highlights the importance of designing inclusive work models that support employees regardless of their gender identity or domestic responsibilities.

From a policy perspective, the present findings call for the development of adaptive human resource practices that can be tailored to different work arrangements. This includes redefining performance metrics in remote contexts, enhancing virtual managerial support, promoting digital autonomy, and investing in mental health infrastructure. Organizations that proactively address these factors are likely to foster a resilient, engaged, and future-ready workforce.

At a societal level, the present research contributes to broader conversations on how India's knowledge economy can sustain psychological well-being alongside economic growth

by highlighting the mental and emotional needs of the digital workforce. As employment trends shift and technology reshapes work boundaries, applying psychological insights to work design becomes essential for national productivity and human capital development. The study, therefore, encourages Indian institutions, both public and private, to prioritize employee experience not just as a company-level concern, but as a national development goal.

To sum up, the present findings confirm that work is not a one-size-fits-all construct. Designing psychologically adaptive work environments will require collaboration between academia, industry, and policymakers. By acknowledging the nuanced impact of work models on employees' psychological states, this study lays the foundation for evidence-based interventions that support not only organizational excellence but also individual fulfillment and societal well-being.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX – 1 (a)

Informed Consent Form

Greetings!

I am Rani Manna, currently pursuing M.Sc. in Applied Psychology at Bethune College, under University of Calcutta. As part of my academic curriculum, I am doing research under the supervision of Dr. Mohua Chatterjee, Department of Psychology, Bethune College. The study aims to explore the impacts of different work arrangements, such as on-site, hybrid, and remote on a number of psychological phenomena among the IT employees of India.

You can help me by participating in the study, if you are working in any IT organization, under any of the above-mentioned modes, for a minimum of one year. The survey will take approximately 15-20 minutes to complete. Your valuable participation will significantly contribute to the success of my research, and I sincerely appreciate your time and effort.

Please be assured that all your responses will remain confidential, and will be used solely for research and academic purposes.

The link of the form is given below:

In case of any further queries or difficulties, you can reach me at:

Mail id – ranimanna4431@gmail.com

WhatsApp No- 6291298843

Your kind cooperation is gratefully acknowledged. Thank you in advance.

Sincerely,

Rani Manna

Consent form

I have fully understood the instructions stated above. I understand that my responses are being collected purely for academic and research purposes only. I understand that my participation in this study is voluntary, and hereby give my consent to participate in this research.

I give my consent.

APPENDICES

APPENDIX – 1 (b)

General Information Schedule (GIS)

Section 1: General Information

1. Name of participant (Initials only):

2. Age of participant:

3. Gender
 - Male
 - Female
 - Non-binary/Other
 - Prefer not to say

4. Educational Qualification
 - B. Tech in Computer Science/IT/related fields
 - B.E. in Computer Science/IT/related fields
 - B.Sc. in IT/Computer Science/related fields
 - BCA (Bachelor of Computer Applications)
 - M.Sc. in IT/Computer Science/related fields
 - Diploma in IT/related fields
 - Certification in IT/Software Development
 - Others (Please specify)

Section 2: Job Details

5. Current Job Role/Position

- Analytics Engineer
- Associate Software Engineer
- Assistant System Engineer
- Business Technology Solutions Associate
- Data Engineer
- DevOps Engineer
- Full Stack Developer
- Implementation Consultant
- Machine Learning (ML) Engineer
- QA Analyst
- R&D Engineer
- Senior Associate Software Engineer
- Software Developer
- Software Engineer
- Software Tester
- UI/UX Developer
- Web Developer
- Others (Please specify)

6. Designation/Level

- Entry-Level
- Junior Associate

- Mid-Level
- Senior-Level
- Manager/Team Lead
- Director/VP
- Consultant
- Freelancer/Contractor
- Others (Please specify)

7. Years of Experience in the IT Sector

- Less than 1 year
- 1 to 3 years
- 3 to 5 years
- 5 to 7 years
- 7 to 10 years
- More than 10 years

8. Years of Experience in the present IT organization (Please select carefully. You will not be able to edit this response later)

- Less than 1 year
- 1 to 3 years
- 3 to 5 years
- 5 to 7 years
- 7 to 10 years
- More than 10 years

9. Current Work Location

- Andhra Pradesh
- Arunachal Pradesh
- Assam
- Bihar
- Chhattisgarh
- Goa
- Gujarat
- Haryana
- Himachal Pradesh
- Jharkhand
- Karnataka
- Kerala
- Madhya Pradesh
- Maharashtra
- Manipur
- Meghalaya
- Mizoram
- Nagaland
- Odisha
- Punjab
- Rajasthan
- Sikkim
- Tamil Nadu

- Telangana
- Tripura
- Uttar Pradesh
- Uttarakhand
- West Bengal
- Andaman and Nicobar Islands
- Chandigarh
- Dadra and Nagar Haveli and Daman and Diu
- Lakshadweep
- Delhi
- Puducherry
- Jammu and Kashmir
- Ladakh

Section 3: Work Arrangement Details

10. What is your Current Work Arrangement/Work Model?

- On-Site (Full-time office work)
- Hybrid (Combination of on-site and remote work)
- Remote/Work from Home (WFH)

11. [If Hybrid] How many days per week do you work remotely?

- 1
- 2

- 3
- 4

12. [If Hybrid] How many days per week do you work on-site?

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

13. Does your role involve frequent overtime?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes

14. Total Length of Experience in Your Current Work Arrangement/Work Model

- Less than 1 year
- 1 to 3 years
- 3 to 5 years
- 5 to 7 years
- 7 to 10 years
- More than 10 years

15. Length of Experience in Your Current Work Arrangement in the present

Organization (Please select carefully. You will not be able to edit this response later)

- Less than 1 year
- 1 to 3 years

- 3 to 5 years
- 5 to 7 years
- 7 to 10 years
- More than 10 years

Section 4: - Family & Household Details

16. Marital Status

- Single,
- Married,
- Divorced,
- Widowed,
- Prefer not to say

17. Do you have children?

- Yes
- No

18. [If Yes] How many children do you have?

- 1,
- 2
- 3
- More than 3

19. Is your spouse employed?

- Yes

- No
- Not Applicable

20. Are you the sole earning member of your household?

- Yes
- No
- Partially – shared with spouse or others

APPENDICES

APPENDIX – 1 (c)

Work-Family Conflict Scale

The following statements describe different ways in which work and family responsibilities may interfere with one another. Please read each statement carefully and indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with it. Use the scale below to rate your responses. 1 –

Strongly Disagree

2 – Disagree

3 – Neutral

4 – Agree

5 – Strongly Agree

There are no right or wrong answers.

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
The demands of my work interfere with my home and family life.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The amount of time my job takes up makes it difficult to fulfill family responsibilities.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Things I want to do at home do not get done because of the demands my job puts on me.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
My job produces strain that makes it difficult to fulfill family duties.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Due to work-related duties, I have to make changes to my plans for family activities.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The demands of my family or spouse/partner interfere with work-related activities.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
I have to put off doing things at work because of demands on my time at home.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Things I want to do at work don't get done because of the demands of my family or spouse/partner.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
My home life interferes with my responsibilities at work such as getting to work on time.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
accomplishing daily tasks, and working overtime.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Family-related strain interferes with my ability to perform job-related duties.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

APPENDICES

APPENDIX – 1 (e)

Work Autonomy Scale

The following statements relate to the level of autonomy you experience in your work. Please read each statement carefully and indicate the degree to which it applies to your current work situation. Use the provided scale to mark your responses accurately.

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Neutral	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I am allowed to decide how to go about getting my job done (the methods to use).							
I am able to choose the way to go about my job (the procedures to utilize).							
I am free to choose the method(s) to use in carrying out my work.							
I have control over the scheduling of my work.							
I have some control over the sequencing of my work activities (when I do what).							
My job is such that I can decide when to do particular work activities.							
My job allows me to modify the normal way we are evaluated so that I can emphasize some aspects.							
I am able to modify what my job objectives are (what I am							

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Neutral	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
supposed to accomplish).							
I have some control over what I am supposed to accomplish (what my supervisor sees as my objectives).							

APPENDICES

APPENDIX – 1 (f)

Job Performance Scale

Please rate each statement below based on your level of agreement, using the following 5-point scale:

- 1: Strongly Disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neutral
- 4: Agree
- 5: Strongly Agree

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
I have the competencies that my job requires.					
I work effectively/efficiently.					
I understand and carry out work-related procedures.					
I work in a planned and organized manner to conclude the task defined to me in full and on time.					
I am eager to acquire new skills related to my job.					
I take extra care and take extra responsibilities while doing my duty.					
I contribute to the creation of a positive working environment in my institution.					
If I encounter a situation that prevents the task from being done, I try to fix it.					
I help and encourage my friends to complete their work.					

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Even if there are criticisms inside or outside the institution, I defend my institution.					
I am proud to be a part of this institution.					

APPENDICES

APPENDIX – 1 (g)

Survey of Perceived Organizational Support Scale (SPOS)

Please read each statement carefully and indicate your level of agreement or disagreement by selecting the appropriate response on the 7-point scale. There are no right or wrong answers; we are interested in your honest opinions about your workplace experiences.

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neutral	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
My organization strongly considers my goals and values.							
My organization really cares about my well-being.							
My organization shows very little concern for me.							
My organization would forgive an honest mistake on my part.							
My organization cares about my opinions.							
If given the opportunity, my organization would take advantage of me.							
Help is available from my organization when I have a problem.							
My organization is willing to help me when I need a special favour.							

